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**Morphotectonic signature of the Campo
Imperatore Quaternary basin
(Central Apennines): implications for
the seismotectonics of Central Italy**

Umberto Fracassi

Tutore:
Prof. Carlo Bartolini

Coordinatore del Dottorato:
Prof.ssa Silvia Iaccarino

Co-tutore:
Dr. Roberto Basili

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Abstract

This research aims at highlighting the small- and medium-scale morphotectonic framework of an intermontane basin emplaced within an area with a multi-phased tectonic history and currently characterized by an unclear seismic regime.

The land-sculpting processes acting upon the Campo Imperatore area (Abruzzi Apennines, Central Italy) are strongly influenced by the structural imprint of the Apennine thrust-belt and the subsequent extensional pattern. An E-W trending branch of a major normal fault system downthrows the back-limb of the chain, thus acting as the northern boundary between the Quaternary floodplain and its surrounding uplands. Prospective conjugate faulting is detected only in restricted areas and away from the influence of two basin thresholds, which triggered terrace deposition and their intermittent dissection. These edges, in turn, may well represent the linkage between the two segments of the E-W fault system.

Adjacent intermontane basins, all of comparable timing and tectonic scenario with the investigated geomorphological domain, record prominent and well-defined seismic histories. Within these areas, seismogenic normal faults with apparently long recurrence intervals have been recognised. Conversely, at Campo Imperatore, no such record is to be found despite its geodynamic environs. Furthermore, while evidences of Late Quaternary normal faulting were recognised in the recent fluvio-glacial sedimentary infill, they notwithstanding yield low-magnitude/high-frequency morphological features.

While brittle tectonics is either scarce or of difficult identification, active drainage system and landscape evolution provide a fresh insight into the subtle dynamics of this basin. Furthermore, new geophysical data, complemented by modelling of coseismic displacement, contributed to demonstrate that Campo Imperatore underwent very recent deformation capable of lowering its S margin. This led to creation of proper accommodation space, towards which high-energy deposits from present-day alluvial fan systems are being conveyed by a shift in tilting of the basin floor.

Active geomorphic evolution indicates a prospectively ongoing deformation, possibly at its inception stage, as suggested by the recently superposed landscapes.

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1. Introduction

This research points toward discrimination, characterization and modeling of the geomorphological signature (BYRD et al., 1994; WOOD, 1996; GILES, 1998; FRACASSI and BASILI, 2001a/b) of an intermontane basin with apparently contradicting morphotectonic evidences, seismic record and tectonic environs. Since all normal deformation within and surrounding Campo Imperatore belongs to the middle Pleistocene and thereafter, and since most if not all of the land sculpting has been preserved while being exerted, present-day landforms are believed to provide a critical clue to (a) geodynamic equilibria in a basin with poor Quaternary land information yet dominated by such Quaternary forms and processes and (b) active deformation in the region (if any).

The Abruzzi Central Apennines form a distinct physiographic and geodynamic province within the *au-large* Apennine edifice. The highest mountain peaks, the widest mountain fronts and some of the most tectonically complex scenarios concentrate here; all of these features are scenically and beautifully embedded within the Gran Sasso Range, where the Campo Imperatore basin is located, on the normal-faulted backbone of the outer Apennine thrustbelt.

Normal faulting flanking Campo Imperatore has been thoroughly investigated as long as Meso-Cenozoic bedrock (VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998) is concerned. This in part due to the fact that research in Quaternary geology flourished during the last 15 years, i.e. the stage from which characterization of seismogenic sources in the densely populated peninsula Italy became a scientific necessity. This, in turn, highlighted a knowledge void, somehow due to lack of sufficient geological evidences from fresh terranes, somehow caused also by a single-sided approach, which was evidently not targeted towards deformation rates and resulting landforms to be tackled.

Furthermore, SW-verging normal faulting in the Central Apennines, by most Authors accepted to be an effect of post-collisional extension (**Fig. 1.1**), does not occur everywhere with the same pattern and, most importantly, with the same intensity and surface expression. This apparently obvious statement is actually needed to perceive the fact that

Figure 1.1. Progressive eastward migration of orogenic wave and subsequent normal fault activity (*after: BASILI, 1999*).

seeking proofs of recent or active faulting may lead to contradictory thought and/or to expect effects of active deformation where they may not occur at all (HUANG et al., 2001). To this end, in-depth and fine-detail geological investigation needs to follow a number of research avenues to demonstrate that selected evidences can be interpreted under an unexpected view (thanks to new data) and that such interpretation can viably contribute to knowledge of recent/ active deformation in the Central Apennines.

This research started from a conspicuous amount of numerical/visual data to highlight subtle surface expression of the Campo Imperatore floodplain. This first step led to the development of a morphotectonic map. It then compared and contrasted geomorphological interpretations with examples from sub-areas deemed to be of particular relevance, which led to a network of new evidences. Further proofs were researched for the most promising of the above information, which led to devise an evolutionary model of the basin and its environs starting from morphotectonic knowledge.

2. Geological framework of Campo Imperatore

The arcuate ridge that hosts the intermontane basin subject to this research underwent a remarkable tectonic history, if compared to the evolution of the Apennines. These pages summarize current knowledge concerning bedrock geology and deformation history of the basin and its geodynamic environs.

2.1 Geodynamic setup of Central Italy

The Apennine thrustbelt resulted from the convergence between the Hercynic European plate and the W-ward subducted Ionian and Paleozoic Adriatic-Apulia lithosphere (ROYDEN et al., 1987; LA VECCHIA, 1988; DEWEY et al., 1989; BIGI et al., 1991; DOGLIONI, 1991; VEZZANI and GHISETTI, 1995; GHISETTI and VEZZANI, 2000). From Oligocene to Pliocene times, the development of an accretionary wedge deformed different stratigraphic sequences of Mesozoic and Tertiary age. Back-deformation of the paleogeographic assemblage composed by Mesozoic terranes involved in the collision suggests that a substantial portion of the Tyrrhenian oceanic lithosphere was subducted. From Oligocene time onwards, continental collision occurred against the Adriatic plate (GHISETTI and VEZZANI, 2000).

Large-scale contraction at the core of the Apennine belt was recently highlighted by deep seismic reflection profiling (PATACCA et al., 1991; BIGI et al., 1991; BIGI et al., 1995). Such imaging underlined the evidence of imbricate structures, detached upon the Triassic Burano anhydrites (GHISETTI and VEZZANI, 2000).

The Late Tertiary collisional system involved the overall Triassic to Late Miocene stratigraphic succession. The upper portion of the sedimentary stack was furthermore overthrust onto Late Miocene – Early Pliocene syn-tectonic foreland units, filled with thick siliciclastic sequences (GHISETTI, 1987). Contraction is highlighted by ~ NE-verging thrusts and folds, while the underlying Hercynic basement was partially involved in decollement layers at various crustal depths (LA VECCHIA, 1988). Inception and development of these contractional structures results from a two-fold deformation history:

- 1) basement and Meso-Cenozoic overburden shorten disharmonically, due to the

underlying detachment in the anhydrites;

- 2) deep-seated thrust ramps ruptured through the sedimentary cover, thus deforming basement chunks and overlying succession.

Arc-shaped mountain fronts (MALINVERNO and RYAN, 1986; DOGLIONI, 1991) remain a peculiar characteristic of this thrustbelt, to date not fully ascertained.

An overview of structural relationships among paleogeographic domains in Central Italy is offered by VEZZANI and GHISSETTI (1998) and CIPOLLARI et al. (1995; **Fig. 2.1**). The Abruzzi Apennines embed the sharpest structures and the tallest peaks of the entire thrustbelt. To the W/NW, these are primarily constrained by the contact between units overlain onto the Latium-Abruzzi carbonate platforms (Late Triassic to Late Miocene) and those belonging to the Umbro-Marchean Apennines; such contact is represented by the Olevano – Atrodoco – Sibillini E-ward front. In this map, Umbro-Marchean terranes are essentially represented by thrustured foreland basins of Miocene age. Units pertaining to the Abruzzi carbonate platform underwent extensive shortening and, thus, built up an imbricate stack and various duplex systems. Their present-day arrangement, however, clearly reflects the extensional regime, essential coaxial with former σ_1 , that provided with the genesis of a large array of intermontane basins of remarkable dimensions (i.e., the Fucino plain). To the N, the Teramo thrust overrode and shortened Upper Miocene flyshes and Triassic platform facies of the Laga Mts. – Montagna dei Fiori group. To the E, the contact occurs with the folded Upper Miocene flyshes and Liassic platform units of the External Abruzzi carbonate system, namely represented by Mt. Morrone and Mt. Maiella. Towards SE, Oligo-Miocene flyshes of the Molise domain are separated from Latium-Abruzzi units by the Val di Sangro tectonic lineament. A similar left-lateral system also separates the Gran Sasso Range from the Morrone – Maiella domains (Avezzano – Bussi line). Plio-Quaternary marine deposits seal thrustured units towards the coastline and host present-day thrusting, in part underneath and partly offshore, as indicated by offshore seismic reflection and seismicity data.

Oligo-Pliocene contraction of Meso-Cenozoic geology found within au-large Central Italy is certainly the result of the geodynamic scenario consisting of extension in the Tyrrhenian and convergence with Adriatic lithosphere. Nevertheless, a number of tectonic lineaments (**Fig. 2.2**), of regional extent and of various orientations, are a marked signature of present-day long-wave topography across almost overall peninsular Italy (WISE et al., 1985; LA VECCHIA, 1988). A two-fold system of quasi-orthogonal families is

Figure 2.1. Geological sketch map of Central Italy (reprinted, from: VEZZANI & GHISETTI, 1998)

recognized, consisting of N100° / N90° and N170°. In some cases, E-W trending ones interrupt the WNW-ESE ones but overall these systems could likely be connected with SEward peninsular stretching of major contractional fronts in the Southern Apennines.

This could be underlined by detection of such lineaments in both inland and offshore into the Tyrrhenian Sea, within an en-echelon transfer fault system (LA VECCHIA, 1988). In some cases, these features have been associated to deep-seated discontinuities. This Author associates these lineaments to pre-existing weakness zones originated during Jurassic extension of carbonate domains and underlines their susceptibility of having been partially reactivated within Plio-Quaternary extensional phases, with a compatible σ_3 . The presence of such shear zones in the crust may have favored and/or triggered displacement transfer from deeper to shallow crustal levels. They could also have exerted a gradient threshold above which lower thrusts up-ramped systematically. With present knowledge

Figure 2.2. Wide-reaching lineaments, already known in the Apennines. They are essentially scale-independent and are highlighted by few main trends. For some features, kinematics and tectonic history is documented; for others, pre-existing discontinuities in the upper crust might be mimicked by the overburden as deformation encounters regional ramps (DEM source: Servizio Geologico d'Italia).

and with lack of a sufficiently fine-spaced deep seismic profiling, this hypothesis cannot be fully pursued; nevertheless it could prove to be most relevant exactly for the Gran Sasso Range, given its WNW-ESE trending branch, in both contractional and extensional scenarios.

Based on industrially-owned data from such seismic lines, BIGI et al. (1995) present a summary cross-section covering the Abruzzi portion of the Apennine thrustbelt (**Fig. 2.3**).

Figure 2.3. *a)* Balanced geological cross-section, from L'Aquila towards the Adriatic coast; *b)* back-deformed cross section. 1) Upper Pliocene – Quaternary; 2) Middle Pliocene; 3) Lower Pliocene siliciclastic deposits (Cellino Fm.); 4) Messinian (Laga Fm.); 5) Cretaceous – Miocene carbonate successions; 6) Jurassic carbonate successions; 7) Trias evaporites; 8) normal fault; 9) thrust; (1) Main outcrops of Rigopiano Conglomerates (*reprinted, from: BIGI et al., 1995*).

The trace of this cross-section was chosen in accordance with the N60° direction of maximum tectonic transport. Back-restoration allowed these Authors to estimate:

- 1) 70 km (45%) shortening for the overall Gran Sasso tectonic unit;
- 2) migration rate of 4 mm/yr for the Messinian foredeep towards E, which they consider to be compatible with retreat velocity due to foreland flexure;
- 3) averaged shortening rate of ~ 20 mm/yr, based on the ages of the deposits sealing thrust fronts.

Basement slab is involved from a depth of 12 km. Most large SW-verging normal structures represent negative inversion of regional-scale thrust ramps. The Gran Sasso tectonic unit overlies a conspicuous regional duplex system.

2.2 Pre-Quaternary geology of the Gran Sasso Range

Having introduced the main reference points for the regional setup surrounding Campo Imperatore, it is now possible to concentrate on bedrock that underlies and circumscribes this basin; the former will be the one against whose geometry and geologic history the latter will be compared and contrasted along the development of this work.

Fig. 2.4 summarizes geology and stratigraphy at the core of the Gran Sasso tectonic unit (ADAMOLI et al., 1982a/b/c; GHISSETTI and VEZZANI, 1986; GHISSETTI, 1987; GHISSETTI and VEZZANI, 1990a; GHISSETTI et al., 1994; BIGI et al., 1996; VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998). To the N, NE and E, numerous thrust sheets imbricate Mesozoic terranes pertaining to the Latium – Abruzzi carbonate platform and their transitional facies. This succession deposited on and across grabens opened in the platform by an early extensional phase (GHISSETTI and VEZZANI, 1990b; BIGOZZI, 1994; BARCHI and BIGOZZI, 1995). Upper Triassic – Lower Jurassic limestone and dolomites (Dolomia and Calcare Massiccio Fms.) sensibly differ from younger channeled bioclastic terranes (Entrochi Calcarenes, Rudista Calcirudites). The latter are frequently interfingering with pelagic units such as Corniola Fm. (Middle Lias), Verde Ammonitico Fm. (Upper Lias – Dogger) and the biomicrites of the Maiolica Fm. (Upper Cretaceous). Numerous bioclastic influxes is also documented for the range Upper Cretaceous – Lower Miocene, exemplified by conspicuous thickness of calcarenites and calcirudites interbedded into the Scaglia Rossa Fm. (Upper Cretaceous – Middle Eocene). These clastic aprons abruptly thin into disappearance in the succession on top of the S-most thrust sheet and in the topographically highest position (GHISSETTI and VEZZANI, 1990b).

Transitional elements between the Latium-Abruzzi and Marche domains are represented by sedimentary evolution from carbonate-based to siliciclastic. The upper section of the Marche succession is actually represented by the Cerrognola Marls (Lower/Middle Miocene), stratigraphically overlain by the Orbulina Marls (Tortonian – Lower Messinian) and the Laga Flysch (Messinian). On disconformal contact, the coarse clastic Mt. Coppe Conglomerates (Messinian - Lower Pliocene *p.p.*) overly and seal variously faulted terranes across the Gran Sasso chain. These polygenic deposits, essentially rudites coarsening upwards into sandstones, were transported on top of the Laga Flysch.

While the geometry development of most thrust sheets does not outcrop, their

Figure 2.4. Simplified geological framework of pre-Quaternary bedrock surrounding the Campo Imperatore basin. Notice the geometric relationships among the overall mountain front, the border fault downthrowing its backlimb and the inner basin. Also notice how the latter (here displayed as a mere alluvial plain) adjusted through and around the bedrock remnants (*redrawn, from: VEZZANI and GHISETTI, 1998*).

termination can be found on the N slope of the Gran Sasso Range (i.e., Teramo Thrust).

Some eroded remnants, bounded by normal faults, either intra-formational or stemming from post-collisional extension, outcrop in the S margin of Campo Imperatore. N120° S-verging normal displacement is a common trait of deformation on both margins. W and E of Mt. Paradiso, however, normal faulting in the S margin displays a different accommodation system. Towards W, NE-SW systems S-verging prevail and generated elongated troughs among the involved Upper Cretaceous terranes; towards E, structures are more loosely-spaced and predominantly N-verging, displacing Jurassic deposits.

The S slope of the Gran Sasso Range was downthrown by the Campo Imperatore border fault, most probably consisting of an array of fault segments, according to the geometry of available outcrops. Stratigraphic displacement for this long structure is thought to exceed 600/700 m (ADAMOLI et al., 1997; VEZZANI and GHISETTI, 1998). The border fault acts a major N boundary for the intermontane basin, acting a slope barrier and a threshold between bedrock and Quaternary infill.

To complement the above information, **Fig. 2.5** underlines the relationships between (a) post-collisional normal faulting and thrusting and between (b) intra-formational normal faulting and pre-Quaternary displacement of comparable geometry (PIANA, 1995). Seven thrust sheets build up the imbricate system of the Gran Sasso Range. However, these faults do not asymptotically merge towards a common detachment level in the hinterland; rather, they are more commonly cut by younger ramps and, eventually, downthrown by high-displacement normal faulting (GHISETTI and VEZZANI, 1990a/b).

Figure 2.5. Geological cross-section between the N shoulder of the Middle Aterno Valley (SW) and the Adriatic foothills (NE) of the Gran Sasso tectonic edifice (reprinted, from: GHISETTI and VEZZANI, 1990a).

2.3 Array of coastal and intermontane basins

Plio-Quaternary sedimentation occurred both on the coastal foothills and modern foreland of the Apennine thrustbelt and in saddles across the chain (**Fig. 2.6**). In most locations, external deposits disconformably sealed Oligo-Miocene flysch deposits (SERVIZIO GEOLOGICO D'ITALIA, 1963; VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998) and marked the stage at which the tectonic edifice started to emerge from the Miocene sea, as the thrustbelt built up and contracted terranes onto the Adriatic subducting slab. Further differential uplift into Pleistocene time favored the genesis of accommodation space along the Abruzzi coastal sector (BIGI et al., 1997). Internal basins, rather, tend to be either accommodated by syn-sedimentary normal fault systems or, in simpler cases, to develop along pre-existing graben or half-grabens (DE LA PIERRE and CLARI, 1994). The latter are predominantly due to NW-SE extensional tectonics (LA VECCHIA, 1988; BIGI et al., 1995b), in part still active (BOSI, 1975; D'AGOSTINO et al., 1994a; CALAMITA et al., 1997; CELLO et al., 1997). A synoptic overview of the terrains documented (*Auct.*) across Campo Imperatore, adjoining basins and coastal depocenters follows in **Table 2.1**.

Figure 2.6. Depositional framework W and E of the Gran Sasso Range and inner intermontane basins of Central Abruzzi (*Auct.*; *DEM source: Servizio Geologico d'Italia*).

INTERNAL (intrabasin) – Quaternary clastic

Age	Location	Terrain	Notes	Author(s)
< 13 ka	W Valle Cortina	Glacial deposits, made up of dolomite clasts, polished and striated, brown micritic limestones and whitish bioclastic calcarenites. In contact with both ash deposits and pre-Quaternary bedrock	<i>Dated by stratigraphic contact</i>	CARRARO & GIARDINO (1992)
13 ka	W Valle Cortina	Ash deposits, reddish sandy material, abundant volcanic glass, augite, and detrital quartz. Direct placement on pre-Quaternary bedrock	<i>Correlated to the emplacement of Tufo Giallo Napoletano</i>	CARRARO & GIARDINO (1992)
Holocene	Coppe di S. Stefano	Moraines, hosted and shown by small depressions, due to dead-ice and karst dissolution. These deposits are connected with 3 expansion phases beyond peak glacial stage.		GIRAUDI (1994) JAURAND (1998)
Holocene	Coppe di S. Stefano to Valle Cortina	Lacustrine sediments, made up of lime and sands, deposited along E-W axis		GIRAUDI (1994)
<< 18 ka	SW M. Brancastello	Colluvial deposits, 5-10 m thick, limited to small remnants, with different facies and basal surface support among them. Made up of dolomite fragments in the W sector, dolomites and micrites towards E. Single sedimentary body, with spatially variable thickness caused by evolution of underlying faults		CARRARO & GIARDINO (1992)
< 18 ka	SW M. Brancastello	Stratified debris (made up of Corniola Fm. fragments), ~50 m thick, forming a 2-term stratigraphic set; the lower dips ~35° SSE, the upper ~20° SSW. Heavily cemented. Several small faults (both normal and reverse), variously oriented (pertaining to the Mandrucce Fault System)		CARRARO & GIARDINO (1992)
18-21 ka (Würm 3)	N M. Scindarella	Glacial moraines	<i>Interpretation of glacial stage</i>	FEDERICI (1979) JAURAND (1998)
15-25 ka (Würm 2)	N M. Scindarella	Glacial moraines	<i>Interpretation of glacial stage</i>	PANIZZA (1985)
22.6 ka	Coppe di S. Stefano to Piano Racollo	Lacustrine sediments	<i>From borehole sample beneath terminal moraines</i>	KOTARBA et al., 2001
Upper Pleistocene to Holocene	NW basin	Coarse moraines, with frontal lobes		FREZZOTTI & GIRAUDI (1990)
31.5-17.5 ka	Rio Fornaca and S M. Camicia	Terraced alluvial deposits. Gravels made up of bioclastic calcarenites, whitish dolomites and micritic limestones. No outcrop of the basal contact. Maximum visible thickness is 40 m. Basal surface of the higher unit is the pre-Quaternary bedrock	<i>¹⁴C dating</i>	FREZZOTTI & GIRAUDI (1992)
Upper Pleistocene	Overall basin	Eolian sediments		FREZZOTTI & GIRAUDI (1990)
75-55 ka (Würm 1)	Overall basin	Lowest stratigraphic unit (basin-floor) - undefined		DEMANGEOT (1965)
Middle Pleistocene	NW region	Moraines, made up of clasts and blocks, sometimes striated, in scarce sandy matrix. Bounded by fluvio-glacial deposits, strongly altered	<i>Interpretation of glacial stage</i>	GIRAUDI (1994)
Middle Pleistocene	Colle Caciario	Cemented breccias, well-stratified, sub-horizontal	<i>No direct dating</i>	GIRAUDI (1994)
< 780 ka	E Piano dell'Ospedale	Stratified debris, pink to light brown, alternate fine to medium-grain, possibly lacustrine deposit, 5-10cm beds, ~20+ (?) m thick body	<i>Fault-bounded towards W. Paleomagnetic dating (Bruhnes chron)</i>	SPERANZA, BASILI & FRACASSI (this work)

EXTERNAL (W of thrustbelt) – Quaternary clastic

Age	Location	Terrain	Notes	Author(s)
9-6.5 ka	Ofena Plain and lower Tirino Valley	Capo d'Acqua gravels and clays, rich in pyroclastic material (feldspars, biotite, clinopyroxenes)	<i>Dated on Mesolithic remains</i>	RADMILL (1984) GIULIANI & SPOSATO (1995)
Upper Pleistocene	Outer Tirino Valley	Capo Spera gravels, alluvial fan facies, with sub-angular breccias, poorly stratified	<i>Dated via morphostratigraphic interpretation</i>	GIULIANI & SPOSATO (1995)
Middle to Upper Pleistocene	Outer Tirino Valley	Bussi depositional units, composed of (a) lacustrine sands and shales, with detrital influx, (b) limestone and sandy clays, with volcanoclastic beds, (c) Carapelle Tuffs, lacustrine clays and sands with thick volcanoclastic influx	<i>Dated on Musterian remains</i>	GIULIANI & SPOSATO (1995)
Middle to Upper Pleistocene	Calascio-Barisciano	Carbonate breccias. Upper unit displays bedding; lower one yields chaotic texture, interspersed with boulders. Fault scarps occur	<i>Reside within fault-bounded suspended valleys and troughs</i>	GALADINI & GIULIANI (1993)
350 ± 50 ka	Svolte di Popoli	Tuff		RADMILL (1984)
Middle Pleistocene	Carapelle Calvisio	Grey and yellow ashes, interbedded with red paleosoils and thin layers made up of carbonate clasts. Vegetal material and leaves suggests a lacustrine-marsh depositional environment	<i>Reside within fault-bounded suspended valleys and troughs</i>	D'AGOSTINO et al. (1994)
Lower to Middle Pleistocene	S. S. Sessanio-Calascio	Lacustrine and fluvio-lacustrine deposits, occasionally bearing coarse material from the carbonate bedrock		BERTINI et al. (1989) D'AGOSTINO et al. (1994)
Lower to Middle Pleistocene	S. S. Sessanio-Calascio	Fonte Vedice Breccias, with carbonate clasts of variable dimensions (from cm to dm scale), sharp-edged, well cemented, carbonate matrix. Bedding is quite evident, layers > 1 m thickness		BERTINI et al. (1989) D'AGOSTINO et al. (1994)
Lower to Middle Pleistocene	Middle Aterno Valley	Limestone alluvial breccias, in lateral contact with fluvial gravel, fining up towards fluvial and lacustrine sands		BOSI & MESSINA (1991)
Lower Pleistocene	Inner Tirino Valley	Convento dei Cappuccini breccias. Basal lacustrine facies, faulted		GIULIANI & SPOSATO (1995)

EXTERNAL (E of thrustbelt) – Plio-Quaternary transitional to continental

Age	Location	Terrain	Notes	Author(s)
Holocene	NE flank of M. Siella	Detrital and eluvial deposits		GHISSETTI & VEZZANI (1986)
Middle Pleistocene	Fano a Como	Well bedded coarse breccias		FREZZOTTI & GIRAUDI (1990)
Lower to Upper Pleistocene	L. Aprutino and along-axis NNW-SSE	Platform pelites to sands and conglomerates with littoral to fluvio-deltaic to continental facies	<i>Emerging line of thrustbelt</i>	VEZZANI & GHISSETTI (1998)
Middle to Upper Pliocene	Penne and along-axis NNW-SSE	Castilenti Fm. Pelites, 400 m thick, transgressive succession upon bedrock units, involved in thrustbelt advancing	<i>Disconformity: emerging sub-limit</i>	ORI et al. (1991) VEZZANI & GHISSETTI (1998)

Table 2.1. Depositional clues within and bounding the Campo Imperatore Basin (Auct.).

2.4 Seismogenic pattern and seismological record

Central Italy is a key case for large destructive earthquakes (BASILI, 1999; BONCIO et al., 1999; BONCIO and BROZZETTI, 1999; TONDI, 1999; GALADINI et al., 2000a/b), in as

much as this certainly applies to the entire peninsula (GRUPPO DI LAVORO CPTI, 1999; BOSCHI et al., 2000; BASILI et al., 2001; BURRATO et al., 2001; VALENSISE and PANTOSTI, 2001) and, au-large, to the active geodynamics of the Tyrrhenian-Apennine system within the Mediterranean framework. These events are predominantly ascribed to normal faulting, either newly-ruptured or extensionally-reactivated thrust splays.

Apart from events with magnitude > ~ 5.5, a sensible amount of less relevant seismicity occurs (BONGIOVANNI et al., 1995; GIULIANI et al., 1999). Various Authors (BLUMETTI et al., 1993; CALAMITA et al., 1997; CELLO et al., 1997; BONCIO et al., 1999; GALADINI et al., 2000a/b) discussed prominent and co-linear arrays of extensional faults, mostly SW-verging,

1) Mt. San Vicino, 2) Mt. Bove-Mt. Vettore, 3) Mt. Gorzano-Campotosto, 4) Gran Sasso (a Como Grande, b Campo Imperatore, c Assergi, d Mt. Cappucciata-S. Vito), 5) Gubbio, 6a) Gualdo Tadino, 6b) Colfiorito, 7a) S. Martino-Mt. Civitella, 7b) Preci-Ancarano R., 7c) Nottoria-Mt. Pizzuto, 8a) Castel S. Maria-Cittareale, 8b) Montereale, 9a) Pizzoli, 9b) Mt. Pettino, 9c) Camarda, 10a) SW Aterno, 10b) Middle Aterno Valley, 11a) Sulmona, 11b) Pizzallo, 11c) Piano d. Cinque Miglia, 12) Mt. Subasio-Spoleto, 13) S. Martani, 14) Rieti Basin, 15) Salto Valley, 16) Mt. Velino, 17) Campo Felice-Piano di Pezza-Ovindoli, 18a) Magnola, 18b) Mt. Parasano, 18c) Gioia dei Marsi, 19a) Mt. Marsicano, 19b) Sangro Valley, 20) Barrea-Castelnuovo a Voltumo

Sasso to Mt. S. Vicino.

deemed to be either active or capable (MACHETTE, 2000) structures (Fig. 2.7). Most (if not all) of such fault systems either bounded or deformed Quaternary intermontane basins across the Apennine thrustbelt (MICCADEI et al., 2001). A significant fraction of such deformation is thought to be causative of recent tectonics, including the Campo Imperatore border fault. BONCIO et al. (1999) downbroke seismogenic fault sets into three main alignments:

- 1) the Westernmost one (Barrea – Fucino – Rieti – Spoleto), bounding the largest intermontane basins;
- 2) the intermediate one (Sulmona – Montereale – Gubbio);
- 3) the Easternmost, from the Gran

Figure 2.7. Recognized SW-throwing normal structures, deemed to be of Quaternary and recent activity s.l. (Auct.) across Central Italy, in part highlighted by fault-wise distinct morphotectonic expression. Notice three aligned mega-sets (from cyan to red). Master faults are named after associated relief or structure (reprinted, from: BONCIO et al., 1999).

The above implies that Campo Imperatore is thought to be part of an actively deforming system at the forefront of the thrustbelt.

However, the Database of Large Seismogenic Sources (i.e., $M > 5.5$) indicates a somewhat different scenario (VALENSISE and PANTOSTI, 2001; **Fig. 2.8**). Such dataset embeds a remarkable amount of information gathered from:

Figure 2.8. Seismicity framework of Central Italy (modified, from: VALENSISE and PANTOSTI, 2001; DEM source: Servizio Geologico d'Italia).

- a) seismogenic sources inferred from geological investigation, geophysical prospecting, paleoseismological trenching, either on literature or specifically conducted;
- b) the Parametric Earthquake Catalogue of Italy, covering the range $\sim 0 - 1999$ A.D.;
- c) events recorded, detected and resolved via the RSN (National Seismic Network, managed by INGV, Roma).

While the latter data source clearly covers a limited time span, it did record the destructive Umbria-Marche 1997 sequence ($M 5.6 / 6.0$; BASILI and MEGHRAOUI, 2001).

These data highlight two main corridors with known seismogenic sources. All of them are large SW-verging normal structures:

- 1) W-ward, best represented by the seismogenic source to which to the 1915 Fucino event (M 7.0) was ascribed. These are associated with large Quaternary basins and moderate-relief mountain fronts;
- 2) E-ward, best represented by the Amatrice-Campotosto (with the 1639, M 5.9 event) and Sulmona basins, bounded by high-relief uplands.

From a regional geology perspective, the second mountain front also includes the Gran Sasso Range. The latter is actually the Eastern-most tectonic edifice with associated depocenters (Campo Imperatore) and an adjacent large SW-verging normal structure, known to have deformed during post-collisional relaxation, i.e. during Upper Pliocene time and possibly onwards (GHISETTI and VEZZANI, 2000; GHISETTI et al., 2001). On the ground of its geometry, extent, structural role at the backlimb of the highest Apennine range and its aligned basins to NW and SE (with well-documented seismogenic sources), such a structure would be a prospectively important candidate for an actively deforming fault, capable of causing large earthquakes. Nevertheless, this does not occur, since either:

- a) the catalogue does not account for a recurrence time (RT) as long as the one this fault entails for its kinematics, or:
- b) the Campo Imperatore border fault is not causing relevant seismicity.

It is important to notice that, in line of principle, data arising from GRUPPO DI LAVORO CPTI (1999) and VALENSISE and PANTOSTI (2001) may suggest that $0.5 < RT < 10$ ka for the Apennine chain and $RT \leq 2$ ka specifically for Central Italy.

On the other hand, minor seismicity ($M < 4.0$) was recently recorded by the Abruzzi local network (**Fig. 2.9**). However, such activity falls outside the research area, mostly concentrating between L'Aquila and Campotosto, for which areas potential seismogenic sources, possibly associated to other relevant earthquakes, are already under examination (VALENSISE and PANTOSTI, 2001).

The above considerations stress the importance of a reliable and complete seismic record. It is herewith advisable that other prospective seismogenic sources could play a role into the present-day kinematics of the Gran Sasso S margin, apart from structures inherited by early deformation stage. In other words, a knowledge gap may occur in Campo Imperatore about its seismic potential. There is a possibility that current information (i.e., actual time-span of the catalogue) prevents us from obtaining an in-depth appraisal of the

seismic-prone capability of this fault.

Figure 2.9. Seismic events recorded in 1994 by the Abruzzi local network. Most significant earthquake entailed $M_w = 3.7$. **a:** hypocentral cross-section; **b:** epicentral locations (modified, from: BONGIOVANNI *et al.*, 1995).

On the other hand, understanding whether the Campo Imperatore border fault is a potentially-active / active source or not has a substantial impact on what we normally expect in currently-deforming extensional environments in Central Italy (assuming it is indeed deforming), where a remarkable and documented degree of seismic hazard requires considerate and in-depth fault characterization. Nevertheless, this work aims at laying the groundwork for a different interpretation of active deformation in this basin. For such purpose, a number of numerical, geophysical and modeling data were employed; the next chapters offer an overview of this integrated dataset and the precision they sought to achieve and exploit.

3. Data: sources, preparation and processing

This research extensively and thoroughly employed an array of available digital data, meant to highlight and exploit the morphological features to be geologically tackled, together with their analytical content. Multiple sources of imagery have been pursued and selected, to obtain numerical and visual data that needed full reorganization, filtering, various degrees of processing and extraction of information. Eventually, a common geographical platform was established to make all data layers fully interoperable and cross-comparable one another.

3.1 Digital Elevation Model

A key dataset in this work consists of fine-detail digital topography. Unlike traditional paper topographic maps, which are static in nature and provide the user only with the final morphological picture, a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) is a matrix of numbers, each representing a height value for any given cell (**Fig. 3.1**; BURROUGH, 1986; ERDAS, 1997; SABINS, 1997). Such a cell corresponds to an actual geographic module of an investigated area, within the precision limits inherent to the sampling technique adopted to generate the matrix. Once calculated, the digital model can then be simply displayed as a traditional contour map, or can be processed for further purposes (§ 3.4, 3.5) which exploit the real nature of such numerical and mathematically self-consistent dataset. The coordinate system, on which the native DEM (and thenceforth the entire dataset) has been generated and geometrically corrected, is an issue by itself and deserved a full paragraph further on.

The final quality (WEIBEL and BRÄNDLI, 1995) of the matrix depends on: (1) the detail and reliability of the original data (e.g., a 1:50.000 map, aerial photo stereo-pairs, sparse point collection on the field); (2) the procedure and precision exploited to translate the original height values into a digital matrix (e.g., digitizing the map, triangulation or kriging of points); (3) the analytical model that filters and organizes the matrix in an array of mathematically realistic values (e.g., algorithms); (4) the final processing needed to correct unexpected false values, data gaps (both altimetric and areal) and non-nature-wise features.

“Regular gridded matrix representation of the continuous variation of relief over space” (BURROUGH, 1986)

Fig. 3.1. Definition of Digital Elevation Model

The very nature of the dataset, after all, is the key quality component, thus fidelity of the DEM (WOOD, 1996) profoundly depends on the actual surface roughness, which can contain information below the resolution limits. Furthermore, recent research in fractal geometry (KLINKENBERG 1992; TURCOTTE, 1997; TUCKER et al., 2001) show that nature-wise variability in surface representation, expressed by degrees of liberty, is never fully achieved; this is in accordance with the fact that no natural measure can be assumed as absolute. While this can be a limitation from a physical viewpoint, it is also important to maintain a functional compromise between the objective of the elevation dataset and its dimensions, which, in case of very high resolution for a large region, can prove to be ineffective due to computing limitations or poor algorithms.

Applications for digital topography span from mere morphological display of land resources (MACMILLAN, PETTAPECE, NOLAN and GODDARD, 1999) to analytical extraction of surface parameters (BURBANK, 1992; NOGAMI, 1995; WOOD, 1996) to coupling of terrain information with diverse geologic features (BLYTHE et al., 2000).

Finally, it is critical to notice the difference between the definitions of Digital Elevation Model and Digital Terrain Model (BURBANK, 1992; WEIBEL and BRÄNDLI, 1995; MILIARESIS, 2001), commonly abbreviated as DTM. While a DEM is solely a number matrix with a height value per cell, a DTM (as the name suggests) embeds explicit information concerning surface representation and morphotypes (WOOD, 1996). In other words, a DTM

may contain a thematic layer above the height data, aimed at describing basic terrain features.

3.1.1 Point source, digitalization, gap fill, geographic reference systems

The original dataset is actually two-fold: the first is at the 1:10.000 native scale, while the second is an excerpt of the Italian national DEM, with a spacing of ~ 230 m. The 1:10.000 scale one is composed of 4 sections of 10 m digitized contours from the Carta Tecnica Regionale (Regional Technical Map), issued by the cartographic division of Regione Abruzzo (Abruzzo Regional Board). The latter licensed these data to Istituto di Ricerca per la Tettonica Recente (a body of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche in Roma) and from the latter leased to the author, under an agreement. The 1:100.000 scale one is the national official dataset (ONORATI et al., 1992), based on the 1 x 1 km cell array provided by Servizio Geologico Nazionale (Italian Geological Survey) and leased to Università di Firenze.

Given its high resolution and appropriate positioning over the area of interest, the first dataset has been primarily exploited, with a minor contribution from the other, more targeted towards basin-scale observation rather than fine-scale analysis, both descriptive and numerical. Data for a DEM commonly derive from either sparse point collection (such as those from photogrammetry – see § 3.2.1 – or a GPS campaign) or contour digitizing; for the key dataset of this work, both procedures needed to be employed.

Source points are those arising from (a) official trigonometric data and (b) leveled points, both from Istituto Geografico Militare (the Italian military cartographic agency). The former entail a near-cm degree of positional fidelity and were also successfully employed to orthorectify airphotos (see § 3.2); the latter were obtained from 1:25.000 official cartography, with ~ 1 m of positional fidelity. As indicated by NOGAMI (1995), a valid system to individuate a surface among such sparse points is a convergent calculation using the harmonic mean. The harmonic computing of elevation z at discrete point (n,m) is:

$$z(t+1) = \frac{z(n-1,m) + z(n+1,m) + z(n,m+1) + z(n,m-1)}{4}$$

where $z(t+1)$ is elevation at the next step of discrete time t . This system offers the opportunity to best choose the grid size for the target DEM, effectively coupled with other

resampling methods (see § 3.1.2).

Contour-based elevation data offers the auto-consistency of values measured along the same track with a known, documented height (the isoline itself) but, on the other end, too many points are sampled along contours and no data across them, thus introducing undersampling (WEIBEL and BRÄNDLI, 1995). However, 1:10.000 contours imply they are 10m-spaced one another and, by adding and interpolating sparse precise points, the final DEM inherited both geometrical limitations and enhanced geographic precision; the end result proved to be an effective compromise.

Nevertheless, digital topography was supplied with a number of imperfections and a significant geographic constraint. The former derived from uneven and possibly non-systematical digitizing, which likely introduced subtle inconsistencies in matching contour terminations among the four sections. The latter was caused by the projection inherited from the original paper cartography. In the first case, double-checking height values for dubious spots was in most case sufficient, connecting loose contour tips; in few situations, especially towards the corner connecting all of the four sections, low-relief terrain interpolators were employed (see § 3.1.2; ERDAS, 1997; DOUCETTE and BEARD, 2000). In the second case, conversely, the overall dataset, before any further procedure, had to be entirely reprojected to a common geographical projection system (**Fig. 3.2**) and, ultimately, in a suitable map reference system (**Table 3.1**).

Fig. 3.2. Geographical projections (modified, from: ERDAS, 1997).

Type	Construction	Property	Use
Geographic	–	–	Angular data entry, spherical coordinates
Mercator	Cylinder	Conformal (True Direction)	Non-polar regions, navigation (straight lines)
Transverse Mercator	Cylinder	Conformal	N-S expanses
Universal Transverse Mercator	Cylinder	Conformal	N-S expanses, data entry, plane coordinates
Oblique Mercator	Cylinder	Conformal	Oblique expanses, satellite tracking
Space Oblique Mercator	Cylinder	Conformal	Satellite imagery
Modified Transverse Mercator	Cylinder	Conformal	Alaska
Albers Conical Equal Area	Cone	Equivalent	Middle latitudes, E-W expanses
Lambert Conformal Conic	Cone	Conformal (True Direction)	Middle latitudes, E-W expanses, flight (straight great circles)
Stereographic	Plane	Conformal	Hemispheres, continents
Polar Stereographic	Plane	Conformal	Polar regions
Polyconic	Cone	<i>Compromise</i>	N-S expanses
Equidistant Conic	Cone	Equidistant	Middle latitudes, E-W expanses
Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area	Plane	Equivalent	Sparse/round expanses
Azimuthal Equidistant	Plane	Equidistant	Polar regions, radio paths (straight great circles)
Gnomonic	Plane	<i>Compromise</i>	Navigation, radio paths (straight great circles)
Orthographic	Plane	<i>Compromise</i>	Globes
General Vertical Near-Side Perspective	Plane	<i>Compromise</i>	Hemispheres
Sinusoidal	Pseudo-cylinder	Equivalent	N-S expanses, equatorial regions
Equirectangular	Cylinder	<i>Compromise</i>	City maps
Miller Cylindrical	Cylinder	<i>Compromise</i>	World maps
Van der Grinten	–	<i>Compromise</i>	World maps
Equivalent Peters	Cylinder	Equivalent	N-S expanses, equatorial regions
Gauss-Boaga	Cylinder	Conformal	Italy

Table 3.1. Synoptic summary of main map projection systems (*after: ERDAS, 1997*). While the geometric solid forms employed to actually project the Earth's surface are clearly imaginable, conformal, equivalent and equidistant mean that angles between lines, areas of expanses and lengths tend to be preserved respectively, all of the above referred to the original Earth-wise geometry. A compromise is sometimes adopted when distorted borders and/or shapes have to be accounted for.

Given the Earth's shape, a map aiming at representing a portion of it needs to be based on a geometrical model viable for the specific planet's surface. To best approximate the Earth's proportions, the following input is needed: (a) a projection system chosen among conventional solid shapes; (b) a datum, representing the zero elevation for a portion or the entire planet (i.e., the geoid); (c) a map reference system.

When projecting the Earth's surface on a given map, the planet is commonly assumed to be a perfect sphere, for either mere ease of representation or when metrically-precise map rendering is not a requisite. Clearly, no such map can claim full geometric

reliability, since the Earth is a rounded, sub-spherical body, with bulges and voids mainly due to rotation, continent-ocean crust alternance and, ultimately, by inner viscosity discontinuities and plasticity. Therefore, on the ground of gravimetric measurements that lead to geoid computation and starting from the differing Earth radiuses at poles and at the equator, such a body is best represented by an oblate spheroid (or ellipsoid), i.e. an ellipse rotated around its shorter axis.

The amount of Earth flattening is expressed as $f = \frac{a-b}{a}$, where a is the equatorial radius (semi-major axis) and b is the polar radius (semi-minor axis). Most map projections rather use eccentricity, expressed as (ERDAS, 1997) $e^2 = 2f - f^2$. In hard numbers, the flattening of the Earth is $\approx 1/300$ and becomes significant in map accuracy at a scale of 1:100.000 or larger.

Calculation of a map projection entails a chosen ellipsoid as to its axes lengths and eccentricity squared (or radius of the reference theoretical sphere). A number of principal spheroids are in use in one or more countries. Differences mainly stem from the differing spots/regions of the globe for which computations were performed, therefore one particular spheroid is conceived for one specific area with given global geometric and geodetic attributes. As it normally happens with any mathematical rendering of a naturally-complex entity, few spheroids can be expected to be the “best fit” for a particular region. The one geometrically consistent with UTM system adopted for this research in the International 1909 (referring to the 1909 International Geophysical Year), with datum European Mean 1950 (ED50).

Maps can be represented within a geographic grid made of lines intersecting each other and separated by either angular or metric offsets. When angles are employed, we clearly refer to Latitude and Longitude, which nevertheless were not used for this research, since they require different dimensions in X and Y due to (a) geometric relationship between the angular components and (b) their variability in function of the exact location on Earth. A metric system was therefore used.

The native projection from which the source map was digitized is Gauss-Boaga, a national reference system, in fact a sub-system of the globally valid Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM); both projections are inverse cylindrical. The former was developed to accommodate the Roma 1940 datum and to employ the Monte Mario zero reference meridian (01° 30' 27" E GMT), so as to obtain a system entirely devoted to Italian

cartography. UTM, however, was the target for all mapping and georeferencing purposes in this work, so the entire DEM from Regione Abruzzo had to be reprojected into the global metric system. Since there is no possibility for a precise geometrical overlap of the two projections, any systematical correction to the X,Y values is mathematically imprecise and, thus, ineffective. To this end, IGM provided conversion factors for each corner of each 1:25.000 map of the Italian landmass; these can be employed for small areas with an acceptable degree of error (double-checked with available imagery). Re-computing the entire matrix was performed at Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, using an in-house code developed by Dr. Roberto Basili.

3.1.2 Surface modeling, triangulation, gridpoint resampling

The matrix obtained as above, gap-filled, re-calculated as if initially digitized from UTM maps, embeds the original data points, arising from both sparse and contour sources; to obtain a DEM, a surface has to be constructed so as to render the dataset uniform and self-consistent. To connect points that are evenly-spaced, a network of new points has to be calculated, redistributed over the exact same geographical space covered by the original

data; this network can be computed via triangulation (**Fig. 3.3**). Using interconnecting triangles, it calculates resampling functions to best reproduce terrain subtleties, within the geometric resolution limits. These limits are a function of the original source sampling rate (as we said, there is a sensible fidelity difference

Figure 3.3. Triangulation network, using either linear or non-linear functions (*redrawn, from: ERDAS, 1997*).

between very sparse points and very close contours – but those points could be very precise from a geographical viewpoint) and the final grid resampling (**Fig. 3.4**). This also leads us to mention the concept of vertical fidelity. Ordinarily, geometric resolution is best when sampling rate is highest, which could however introduce error due to oversampling (i.e., between two original cell values a third is added with an intermediate value, which could be geographically untrue); this makes geometric resolution a very important issue when

observation of terrain features is involved.

On the other hand, vertical resolution is no less important, in as much as a DEM is used to obtain reference height values, thus appropriate and reliable elevation data is an asset. Vertical fidelity essentially depends on the quality of source height data but, as it is clear, both resolution types are critical to a good quality DEM.

Resampling can be performed with models: (a) Nearest Neighbor (Fig. 3.5), where

output pixel is assigned the value of the closest one; (b) Bilinear Interpolation (Fig. 3.6), where output pixel value is computed across a 2 x 2 window with a bilinear function and (c) Cubic Convolution (Fig. 3.7), where output pixel value is computed across a 4 x 4 window with a cubic function.

Figure 3.4. Resampling a source digital image, bearing neither geographic referencing nor geometric corrections, to map a chosen output grid into a projection system (redrawn, from ERDAS, 1997).

Figure 3.5. Nearest neighbor. Of the four pixels, the closest is adopted as reference. The new interpolated value will be the same as the black dot's (redrawn, from ERDAS, 1997).

Figure 3.6. New pixel position after bilinear interpolation. r is the location of the re-transformed coordinate (redrawn, from ERDAS, 1997).

Figure 3.7. Convolution on a 16-pixels matrix. Since a cubic (rather than linear) function is employed, the farther pixels are from (x_r, y_r) , the less exponentially they weight (redrawn, from ERDAS, 1997).

The former resampling method was the most employed and an outline follows.

To identify the 16 pixels in relation to the retransformed coordinate (x_r, y_r) , the pixel (i, j) is used so that (ERDAS, 1997):

$$i = \text{int}(x_r)$$

$$j = \text{int}(y_r)$$

with (x_r, y_r) expressed in data file coordinates (pixels); pixels around (i, j) make up a 4x4 grid. The formula used in this work is that embedded in ERDAS Imagine 8.3.1:

$$V_r = \sum_{n=1}^4 V(i-1, j+n-2) \times f[d(i-1, j+n-2)+1] + V(i, j+n-2) \times f[d(i, j+n-2)] + V(i+1, j+n-2) \times f[d(i+1, j+n-2)-1] + V(i+2, j+n-2) \times f[d(i+2, j+n-2)-2]$$

where:

$d(i, j)$ = distance between a pixel with coordinates (i, j) and (x_r, y_r)

$V(i, j)$ = data file value of pixel (i, j)

V_r = output data file value

$f(x)$ = the following function:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} (a+2)|x|^3 - (a+3)|x|^2 + 1 & \text{if } |x| < 1 \\ a|x|^3 - 5a|x|^2 + 8a|x| - 4a & \text{if } 1 < |x| < 2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where $a = -0.5$ (a constant which differs in other applications of cubic convolution), a value which tends to produce output data with a mean and standard deviation closer to those of original data (ERDAS, 1997).

Advantages

Uses 4x4 resampling. In most cases, mean and standard deviation of the output pixels match those of input pixels more closely than any other resampling method.

The effect of the cubic curve weighting can both sharpen image and smooth out noise. Actual effects depend upon dataset.

Suited for drastically changing data cell size, such as in Landsat TM/airphoto merges.

Disadvantages

Data values may be altered (may not be recommended for classification use afterwards).

The most computationally-intensive and, therefore, the slowest resampling method.

Not recommended for qualitative-wise data

Table 3.2. Synoptic summary of bicubic convolution resampling (after: ERDAS, 1997).

The following interpolation procedures, suited for raster image editing specifically for DEMs (ERDAS, 1997) were employed to further refine the final elevation dataset:

- 2D polynomial – surface approximation
- Multi-surface functions – with least squares prediction

- Distance weighting

2D polynomial provides faster interpolation than weighting and multi-surface functions (ERDAS, 1997). ERDAS Imagine 8.3.1 employs the following equation:

$$V = a_0 + a_1x + a_2y + a_3x^2 + a_4xy + a_5y^2 + \dots$$

where:

V	= data value (elevation for DEM)
a	= polynomial coefficients
x	= x coordinate
y	= y coordinate

Multi-surface functions provide the most accurate results for DEM created through automatic extraction (i.e., from airphoto overlap; ERDAS, 1997 and references therein). The following equation is embedded into ERDAS Imagine 8.3.1:

$$V = \sum W_i Q_i$$

where:

V	= output data value (elevation for DEM)
W_i	= coefficients derived by the Least Squares Method
Q_i	= distance-related kernels interpretable as continuous single-value surfaces

The weighting function determines how the output data values will be interpolated from a set of reference data points (ERDAS, 1997). For each pixel, the values of all such points are weighted by a value corresponding with the distance between each point and the pixel. The weighting function applied in ERDAS Imagine 8.3.1 is: $W = \left(\frac{S}{D} - 1\right)^2$, where S is the normalization factor and D is the distance from output data point and reference point. The value for any given pixel is calculated by taking the sum of weighting factors for all reference points, multiplied by the data values of those points and dividing by the sum of the weighting factors (ERDAS, 1997 and references therein):

$$V = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i \times V_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i}$$

where:

- V = output data value (elevation value if a DEM)
 i = i^{th} reference point
 W_i = weighting factor of point i
 V_i = data value of point i
 n = number of reference points

The final product is an effective image of the topography in the chosen area, with a geometric resolution approaching 10 m x 10 m (**Fig. 3.8**).

Figure 3.8. DEM gridded, interpolated, gap-filled and filtered from the 1:10.000 sections of Carta Tecnica Regionale (*source contours courtesy IRTR – CNR; © Regione Abruzzo*).

3.2 Airphotos

The visual interpretation basis for this work consists of a geometrically-consistent,

geographically-verified and mathematically-modeled array of scanned aerial photographs, at the 1:33.000 scale, leased by Istituto Geografico Militare to Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, who kindly provided the data and scanning facilities. Whereas stereoscopy is ordinarily the preferred medium for photogeological interpretation, a digital solution was chosen; the purpose was to obtain a self-consistent visual database, reliable both on the visual and, most importantly, the geometric and geographic grounds. Therefore, 9 photographic frames, with sufficient overlap and sidelap (**Fig. 3.9**) were converted to raw digital images, inheriting three main constraints:

- 1) deformation due to flight altitude/position, acquisition geometry, high-relief terrain;
- 2) tonal discrepancies among the gray-scale photographic prints;
- 3) no geographic reference was embedded.

Figure 3.9. Geometry and relationships among blocks of aerophotographs, as taken on two flight strips. A block of airphotos consists of parallel strips, with a moderate sidelap (*redrawn, from: ERDAS, 1997*).

To explain the first point, the overall geometry of an airphoto should be summarized first. The exterior orientation (**Fig. 3.10**) of an aerial camera determines the relationship of an airborne image to the ground coordinates system. Such orientation parameters allow post-processing of the scanned aerial photograph, thus correcting the image for inherent distortion and terrain relief.

- where:
- PP = Principal Point of Autocollimation
 - O = perspective center with ground coordinates (X_0, Y_0, Z_0)
 - $[O-x, O-y, O-z]$ = image space coordinate system, with origin in O and the x/y axes parallel to the image coordinate system
 - X_G, Y_G, Z_G = ground coordinates
 - $[O-X', O-Y', O-Z']$ = a local coordinate system parallel to the ground one but with its origin in O. Used to express ω, ϕ, κ rotation angles
 - P_1 = point in the image plane of spatial coordinates $(x, y, -f)$
 - f = focal distance of camera lens (in mm)
 - P_G = point on the ground of coordinates (X_G, Y_G, Z_G)
 - l = metric distance between O and P_G
 - X, Y, Z = reference coordinates.

Figure 3.10. External and internal geometry of an aerial photogrammetric camera (redrawn, from: ERDAS, 1997).

The relationship among image coordinates, ground coordinates and orientation parameters is described by the collinearity equations (ERDAS, 1997):

$$x = -f \frac{r_{11}(X_G - X_0) + r_{21}(X_G - Y_0) + r_{31}(X_G - Z_0)}{r_{13}(X_G - X_0) + r_{23}(X_G - Y_0) + r_{33}(X_G - Z_0)}$$

$$y = -f \frac{r_{12}(X_G - X_0) + r_{22}(X_G - Y_0) + r_{32}(X_G - Z_0)}{r_{13}(X_G - X_0) + r_{23}(X_G - Y_0) + r_{33}(X_G - Z_0)}$$

where:

- x, y = image coordinates
- $r_{11} - r_{33}$ = coefficients of a 3x3 rotation matrix defined by angles ω, ϕ and κ that transforms the image system to the ground system.

Positional errors are further raised by image inner distortions due to the very acquisition geometry (**Fig. 3.11**). Tonal discrepancies are somewhat unavoidable and unpredictable, depending on the film employed, exposure, sun radiation at nadir view and film development.

Figure 3.11. Sketch of geometric distortion (Δd) inherited by terrain points distant from nadir view. R is local Earth curvature at nadir point, H is flying height of satellite above known datum at nadir point, d is the distance of image point from nadir, z is the elevation of ground point, α is the angle between nadir and image point before adjustment for terrain displacement and β is the angle between nadir and image point in vertical view (redrawn, from ERDAS, 1997).

To this end, image processing is a substantial help but, whereas correcting a single, unitary image can be generally simpler, adjoining images expressing a geologic entity in two strongly different tones cannot be altered separately. Also, due to radial light diffusion caused by the very curved lenses employed in aerial photcameras (with a deep focal length), a darkening effect tends to be more prominent towards the frame borders and, maximally, at corners.

Spatial resolution primarily depends on the sensor's characteristics (for satellite images) and inner geometry, while it mainly remains into the camera optics, film properties and scanning resolution for scanned airphotos. In the first case, the Instantaneous Field of View (IFOV) is a measure of the area viewed by a single detector in a given instant in time (ERDAS, 1997 and references therein). For instance, Landsat MSS (MultiSpectral Sensor, now no longer employed) yields an IFOV of 79 x 79 m but, since there is an overlap of 11.5 m in each pass of the scanner, the actual area covered by any single pixel in the final data is 56.5 x 79 m.

Although the IFOV is not precisely corresponding to the final geometric resolution, it is important to know the number of pixels into which the total field of view for the image is broken. Objects smaller than the target pixel size may still be recognizable in the final image if they contrast with the background, road network, drainage pattern, etc. Conversely, objects the same size of the final pixel (or larger) may not be detectable if there are brighter or more dominant objects nearby.

As previously said, a scanned image holds no geographical referencing and, to this end, it has to be projected and mapped to a chosen reference system. For all georeferencing purposes, the DEM has been used as a common geographic basis. The purpose was to obtain an orthographic image.

3.2.1 Orthorectification

A digital orthophoto (**Fig. 3.12**) is a representation of the surface, as imaged by the aerial camera, projected onto the plane of zero elevation (datum), its reference plane. To create a digital orthorectified airphoto, the following was employed:

- the scanned aerial photograph(s)
- the reference DEM
- orientation parameters and inner geometry details of the camera.

Figure 3.12. Digital image draped onto DEM (*redrawn, from: ERDAS, 1997*).

Relief displacement was corrected for by taking each pixel of the DEM and finding the equivalent position in the airphoto. The trigonometric data points used to enhance the DEM were here employed as Ground Control Points (GCP), i.e. points for which a very high degree of geographic fidelity can be assumed. A brightness value is determined for this location based on resampling of the surrounding pixels. Brightness, elevation and orientation were used to compute the location in the orthoimage file. Such an image is essentially free from significant geometric distortions, normally yielding a very high degree of terrain fidelity.

The overall quality of the image clearly depends from a number of factors. When mapping a raster image, such as a digitized airphoto, in a new reference system, resampling the original pixel grid with the new geographic information was clearly the next step. Image geometric transformations were employed to remap images from one projection (or from raw imagery) to the target map projection. Resampling thus takes charge of correcting, rectifying

or distorting the assemblage of pixels that will constitute the target dataset.

Main cause	Inherent details
Airphoto geometry	Camera orientation, lens structure, film sensitivity, flight route, altitude shifts, change in aircraft buoyancy due to mountain-to-valley passages
Atmospheric interference	Aerosol, surface heat reflectivity; atmospheric distortions, Earth's curvature, Earth rotation, orbital position shifts (especially for spaceborne imagery)
Resampling, projection	Interpolation method, precision of projection parameters, precision of GCPs, transformations between projection systems
DEM source, quality	Topography acquisition (i.e., scanned, digitized, etc), data spacing and distribution (i.e., from contours, regular grid, photogrammetry-derived), scale of measurements

Table 3.3. *Orthophoto constituents and constraints* (after: ERDAS, 1997).

A transformation matrix is a set of coefficients computed from the GCPs to be inserted into polynomial equations. A minimum number of points are necessary to calculate the function, depending on the order of the transformation. This number of points is (ERDAS, 1997):

$$\frac{(t+1) \cdot (t+2)}{2}$$

where t is the order of the transformation. The transformation matrix contains the coefficients for transforming the reference coordinate system to the input one, as this is applied in ERDAS Imagine 8.3.1. Therefore, the units of the residuals and RMS errors are the units of the input coordinate system.

The transformation matrix was tested by comparing the known source GCP coordinates to coordinates for the same point in the input coordinate system that are calculated with the matrix. The corresponding reference GCPs were retransformed to the input coordinate system using the reference-to-input transformation matrix. The distance between the input GCP coordinates and these retransformed coordinates is the RMS error. It is calculated by the root means squared method using the following equation (ERDAS, 1997):

$$\text{RMS} = \sqrt{(x_r - x_i)^2 + (y_r - y_i)^2}$$

where:

- x_i, y_i = source coordinates
- x_r, y_r = retransformed coordinates.

RMS error is expressed as a distance in the input coordinate system. If data file coordinates are the input coordinates, then the RMS error is a distance in pixel widths. The distances between the input and retransformed coordinates in one direction are called residuals. Each GCP yields an error with respect to the computed geometric model; this is calculated with a distance formula as follows (ERDAS, 1997):

$$R_i = \sqrt{XR_i^2 + YR_i^2}$$

where R_i is the RMS error and XR_i and YR_i X and Y residuals respectively. From the residuals, the following calculations are performed by ERDAS Imagine 8.3.1 to obtain the total RMS error:

$$R_x = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n XR_i^2} \qquad R_y = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n YR_i^2}$$

$$T = \sqrt{R_x^2 + R_y^2} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n XR_i^2 + YR_i^2}$$

where:

R_x	= X RMS
R_y	= Y RMS
T	= total RMS
n	= number of GCPs
i	= GCP number

Additionally, all points contribute to the error, within the constraints (ERDAS, 1997):

$$E_i = \frac{R_i}{T}$$

where:

E_i	= error contribution
R_i	= RMS error per GCP
T	= total RMS

Image transformations, like most operations to be performed in image processing, can be 1st-order (linear) or 2nd-(or higher) order (nonlinear).

Linear transformations (**Fig. 3.13**) entail a first-order polynomial for x and y, under

the form (ERDAS, 1997):

$$x_0 = b_1 + b_2 x_i + b_3 y_i \qquad y_0 = a_1 + a_2 x_i + a_3 y_i$$

where:

x_i, y_i source coordinates

x_0, y_0 rectified coordinates

a_n, b_n .. the six coefficients of the transformation matrix

A first-order transformation can accommodate for (ERDAS, 1997):

- location in X and/or Y
- scale in X and/or Y
- skew in X and/or Y
- rotation.

Such transformations are used to project raw imagery to a planar map, convert between different planar map projections and to rectify images covering relatively small areas.

Nonlinear transformations (**Fig. 3.14**) are suited for distortions that can be analytically represented only by higher-order functions. The process is also known as rubbersheeting, which was used for airphoto and image resampling after triangulation (§ 3.2). It employs the following equations (ERDAS, 1997):

$$x_0 = \sum_{i=0}^5 \sum_{j=0}^i a_k x^{i-j} y^j \qquad y_0 = \sum_{i=0}^5 \sum_{j=0}^i b_k x^{i-j} y^j$$

with 21 coefficients for each polynomial to be determined. To solve the above, first- and second-order derivatives are employed for each vertex of the triangle, thus providing 18 conditions; the remaining 3 needed for the solution stem from the assumption that the partial derivative for each edge of the triangles is a cubic polynomial, implying that the sum of the polynomial items beyond the third-order produce a zero value (ERDAS, 1997).

Second-order transformations were used to convert Lat/Lon data to a planar projection, for data covering a large area (to account for the Earth's curvature), and with distorted data (for example, due to camera lens).

Third-order transformations were specifically used with distorted aerial photographs but are

generally targeted at scans of warped maps and radar imagery.

Fourth-order transformations are called by ERDAS Imagine 8.3.1 routines for very distorted aerial photographs.

The transformation matrix of order t contains the coefficients $2 \sum_{i=1}^{t+1} i$. The multiplier 2 is needed for the two sets of coefficients – one for X and one for Y. An easier way to achieve the same result is: $(t+1) \times (t+2)$. Clearly, the size of the transformation matrix increases with its order. The polynomial equation for a t -order transformation is (ERDAS, 1997):

$$x_0 = A + Bx + Cy + Dx^2 + Exy + Fy^2 + \dots + Qx^i y^j + \dots + \Omega y^t$$

where $A, B, C, D, E, F \dots Q \dots \Omega$ are coefficients and i, j are exponents. All combinations of x^i times y^j are used in the polynomial expression, so that $i + j \leq t$. The equation for y_0 takes the same format with different coefficients.

Figure 3.13. Image transformations performed by linear functions (*redrawn, from: ERDAS, 1997*).

Figure 3.14. Image transformations performed by nonlinear functions (*modified, from: ERDAS, 1997*).

An example of how effectively an airphoto can be deformed back to its theoretical geometry using orthorectification is visible in **Fig. 3.15**. In **Fig. 3.16**, the overall resulting orthophotomap is displayed, within its UTM grid.

Figure 3.15. Effects of DEM-based rectification of an airphoto (depicting Mt. Camicia, Mt. Prena and the conspicuous alluvial fans on the S border of the Gran Sasso chain). Notice the substantial shrinkage in width around the very peaks; the airphoto is back-deformed from its flattened shot to the actual heightened position across the drainage divide. Also notice the irregular red frame, indicating the true amount of geometric distortion inherited by the photograph due to flight altitude, yaw, pitch and roll.

3.3 Landsat TM image

For limited purposes, mostly devoted to augment visualization of investigated terrains, a Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM) image was employed, on lease from Istituto per l'Agrometeorologia e l'Analisi Ambientale Applicata all'Agricoltura (a body of Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche in Firenze). A brief outline of these data follow.

The Thematic Mapper scanner is a multispectral scanning system capable of recording reflected/emitted energy from the visible, reflective infrared, middle infrared and thermal infrared regions of the electromagnetic spectrum (**Table 3.4**; SABINS, 1997). TM yields a swath width of ~ 185 km from a height of 705 km. It is best suited to land use, land cover, soft-rock / hard-rock discrimination, soil moisture etc. Its spatial resolution is 28.5 x 28.5 m for bands 1-5 and 7, 120 x 120 m for band 6 and 15 x 15 m for band 8 (in the ETM+ sensor mounted on the last platform, Landsat 7). Radiometric resolution is 8-bit, implying that data pixel values for any single band range from 0 to 255.

Figure 3.16. Overlap of orthorectified aerial photographs covering Campo Imperatore and the surrounding Gran Sasso Range. Notice DEM-warped borders of single airphotos, especially across high-relief zones, and their tonal contrast due to difference in photographic reproduction prior to data digital acquisition.

Airphotos © Istituto Geografico Militare Italiano

Band N.	Wavelength range	Chromatic target	Use
1	0.45 – 0.52 μm	Blue - visible	Coastal waters, soil/vegetation threshold, forest type, road network
2	0.52 – 0.60 μm	Green - visible	Green reflectance of healthy vegetation
3	0.63 – 0.69 μm	Red - visible	Discriminates between many plant species. Soil/rock boundaries, geological markers, lineations
4	0.76 – 0.90 μm	Reflective infrared	Highlights vegetation biomass, soil/crop and land/water contrasts
5	1.55 – 1.74 μm	Middle infrared	Highlights water content in plants. Discriminates among clouds, snow and ice
6	10.40 – 12.50 μm	Thermal infrared	Vegetation and crop stress detection, heat intensity and geothermal sources
7	2.08 – 2.35 μm	Middle infrared	Discriminates lithologies, soil boundaries and soil and vegetation moisture content
8	–	Panchromatic	

Table 3.4. Summary of multispectral performances in Landsat 4/5 TM & 7 ETM+ data (from: ERDAS, 1997).

The sensors on remote sensing platforms record electromagnetic radiation. This is valid within the terrain's response range and as permitted by the physical, electronic and transmission constraints yielded by the scanner (or transceiver, film, etc.). Therefore, the spectrum (Fig. 3.17) needed to define and ascertain sensors' bands is a resultant of:

- the quantity and quality of radiation retransmitted from the Earth,
- interferences from the atmosphere and
- the actual capabilities of the sensor to detect and record such information.

Figure 3.17. Array of frequencies as sunlight is absorbed, diffracted, refracted and eventually re-transmitted by the Earth's surface. SWIR and LWIR respectively indicate short-wave and long-wave infrared (from: ERDAS, 1997).

The overall spectrum covers the entire range of electromagnetic radiation, spanning from cosmic very-long-range waves to radio waves. This obviously encompasses visible and near-visible optical waves, resulting from the energy of the Sun as it is absorbed, diffracted and reflected by the conspicuous variety of terrain targets upon the Earth's surface.

Although this work didn't entail a multi-sensor approach as per the sought remote sensing information, it is important to highlight that a large number of commercial satellites fly various scanners, with a variable amount of spectral, geometric and radiometric characteristics (qualities as well as limitations). Landsat MSS (today no longer in use) and, soon afterwards, TM were mere icebreakers in the remote sensing industry, today in full production and growing. A summary of main commercial sensors is available in **Table 3.5**.

Since all categories of land cover (lithotypes, water bodies, railroad, grass etc.) behave very distinctively upon radiation, due to their specific physical nature and chemical/organic structure, most (if not all) surface elements yield a distinguishable electromagnetic signature, i.e. a characteristic frequency and distribution of pixels within a given spectral range.

	Landsat TM	SPOT	IRS-1/C	Ikonos	Aster	SAR	Aerophoto
Type	Passive 7/8 bands Includes IR	Passive 1/3 bands	Passive 3 bands	Passive 1/4 bands Includes IR	Passive 12 bands Includes IR	Active Amplitude and phase	Passive 1/+ bands Also with IR
Resolution	28.5 m 15m (ETM+)	10 m (Pan) 20 m (MS)	5 m	1 m (Pan) 4 m (MS)	15-90 m	Computed 8 - 20 m	Sampling-dependent < 0.5 m
Target	Land use, geology	Land use, geology, DEM	Geology, land use	Cadastry, geology, DEM	Lithotype discrimination, water content, thermal capacity	Interferometry, DEM	Geomorphology, DEM
Scale	1:50.000	1:25.000	1:10.000	< 1:10.000	1:25.000 - 1:50.000	1:25.000	< 1:10.000
Coverage	Entire landmass	Almost entire landmass	On-demand	On-demand	On-demand	Almost entire landmass and on-demand	National territories and on-demand
Advantages	Large extents, relatively affordable, multispectral	Precise	Very precise, multispectral	Excellent geometric resolution	High IR sensitivity	No other sensors perceive this information	Photographic nature of images is the most reliable
Limits	Coarse resolution constrains uses	Expensive for its small footprint	Not very much supported	Still very expensive	Calibration is still imperfect	Technology is time-consuming and expensive	Sometimes with severe inner deformations
Availability	USGS, ESA, NASA, Dealers	CNES, USGS, ESA, NASA, Dealers	USGS, ESA, Dealers	Space Imaging, Dealers	NASA	ESA, Radarsat, USGS, Dealers	Local and regional boards, national cartographic agencies
Costs	Max 600 \$	1000 \$ or free for small areas	1000 \$	~20 \$/km ²	Free	500 \$ +	Variable

Table 3.5. Principal types of commercially-available remote sensing data.

Having determined most signatures for a variety of sensors' specifications, radiation

conditions and target non-isotropic features, it is possible to analyze an image's histogram and band combination, in order to make assumptions about the scene that generally prove to be fairly reliable, in as much as they are based onto hard data.

Where multispectral imagery provides with its best capabilities is indeed via its inherent contrast, as it is maximized by chromatic distribution in response to the target's electromagnetic properties. Stretching and its variants (Figs. 3.18, 3.19) enhance the distribution (histogram) of pixels as a function of such response.

Figure 3.18. Transformation in pixel distribution. Note breakpoints at left and right of input histogram (in gray) (redrawn, from: ERDAS, 1997).

A number of mathematical transformations (**Table 3.6**) can be employed, after histogram correction, to enhance the remote sensing data response; this clearly depends from the sensor and the target. These functions mainly aim at adapting either spatial, spectral or radiometric characteristics of the image, normally in a combination of the above.

Figure 3.19. Contrast stretch obtained manipulating linear transformation functions and their effect on output histogram (redrawn, from: ERDAS, 1997).

With spatial enhancement, the goal is to refine the geometrical resolution of the input image, for instance superposing and interpolating two datasets, one of which with a sensibly finer resolution. Results can provide with a 'virtual image', i.e. a multispectral dataset such as Landsat TM with a small pixel size, which the sensor cannot nominally record. Radiometric functions aim at correcting or refining limitations inherent to a scanner's sensitivity and to the error factors introduced by lower atmosphere aerosol content: this, for instance, can sometimes sensibly alter the way a sensor discriminates and records certain wavelengths. Spectral enhancements deal with the sensor's capabilities to actually separate band contributions to the overall contrast image.

Function	Description
SPATIAL ENHANCEMENT	
Use values of individual and surrounding pixels	
Convolution	Uses a matrix to average small sets of pixels across an image
Non-directional Edge	Averages the results from two orthogonal 1 st derivative edge detectors
Focal Analysis	Process similar to convolution filter, applied to class values
Texture	Defines texture as a quantitative characteristic in an image
Adaptive Filter	Varies the contrast stretch for each pixel as a function of the DN values in the surrounding shifting window
Statistical Filter	Averages pixels within a shifting window that fall within a statistically-defined range
Resolution Merge	Merges imagery of different spatial resolutions
Crisp	Sharpens the overall scene luminance without distorting the thematic content of the image
RADIOMETRIC ENHANCEMENT	
Use values of individual pixels within each band	
Lookup Table Stretch	Output image contains data values as modified by a lookup table
Histogram Equalization	Redistributes pixel values with a non-linear contrast stretch so that there are approximately the same number of pixels with each value within a range
Histogram Match	Mathematically determines a lookup table that will convert the histogram of one image to resemble the histogram of another
Brightness Inversion	Allows both linear and non-linear reversal of the image intensity range
Noise Reduction	Removes noise using an adaptive filter
SPECTRAL ENHANCEMENT	
Transform the values of each pixel on a multiband basis	
Principal Components Analysis (PCA)	Compresses redundant data values into fewer bands which occur to be more interpretable than the source data
Inverse Principal Components	Performs an inverse of the PCA
Decorrelation Stretch	Applies a contrast stretch to the PCA of an image
Tasselled Cap	Rotates the data structure axes to optimize data viewing for vegetation studies
RGB to IHS	Transforms red, green and blue values to intensity, hue and saturation ones
IHS to RGB	Inverse of the above
Indices	Performs band ratios that are commonly used in mineral and vegetation studies
Natural Color	Simulates color for Landsat TM data (<i>Red = 3, Green = 2, Blue = 1</i>)
FOURIER ANALYSIS	
Commonly applied towards Synthetic Aperture Radar data	
Fourier Transform (FT)	Discrete Fourier Transform application
Inverse Fourier Transform	Computes the inverse 2D Fast Fourier Transform of the spectrum
Fourier Magnitude	Converts the FT output in an image displaying FT order of magnitude(s)
Homomorphic Filter	Enhances imagery using an illumination/reflectance model

Table 3.6. Modeling functions available for image enhancement (*after: ERDAS, 1997*).

In this work, both Principal Component Analysis and Brovey formulas were employed for resolution merge purposes. The objective was to produce a highly contrasted image (something that only the TM dataset could achieve) with the inner geometric fidelity of the airphoto orthomosaic. ERDAS Imagine 8.3.1 embeds the three widely accepted methods of transformation when merging different datasets (ERDAS, 1997 and references therein):

- Forward-reverse Principal Components
- Multiplicative
- Brovey

Principal Components Merge is primarily aimed at Landsat TM images, namely its 28.5 m bands (1-5 and 7). Naturally, the procedure is mathematically thorough on any multispectral imagery, even those arising from recent high-resolution sensors (like IRS-1/C – 5 m), as long as the goal is then to blend datasets with sensibly different geometric resolution and radiometric features. PC technique assumes that (ERDAS, 1997):

- a) PC-1 contains only overall scene luminance, while all interband variation is taken charge of by the remaining 5 PCs;
- b) Scene luminance in the SWIR (Short-Wave InfraRed, i.e. TM bands 4 & 5) is identical to visible scene luminance.

The above is the groundwork for the forward transform. PC-1 is removed and its numerical range (min to max) is computed. The high spatial resolution image is then remapped to keep its histogram curve constant but in the same numerical range as in PC-1. It is then substituted for PC-1, thus applying the reverse transform. The latter remapping is performed while not interfering with the thematic information (ERDAS, 1997).

Of the resolution merge techniques, PC is the most computation intensive. It is the best method when the goal is preserving the original radiometric quality in the final product.

The Brovey transform (developed by Dr. Bob Brovey, Exxon Oil Co.), limited to 3 bands per time, is described by the following formula (ERDAS, 1997):

$$\frac{DN_{B1}}{DN_{B1} + DN_{B2} + DN_{B3}} \cdot DN_{HR} = DN_{newB1}$$

Given two images, such as a Landsat TM and a panchromatic (i.e., grayscale) airphoto, the

calculation is as follows:

$$\text{RED} = \text{B5:1.65}_{\mu\text{m}} / (\text{B2:0.56}_{\mu\text{m}} + \text{B4:0.83}_{\mu\text{m}} + \text{B5:1.65}_{\mu\text{m}}) * \text{B8:0.65}_{\mu\text{m_PAN}}$$

$$\text{GREEN} = \text{B4:0.83}_{\mu\text{m}} / (\text{B2:0.56}_{\mu\text{m}} + \text{B4:0.83}_{\mu\text{m}} + \text{B5:1.65}_{\mu\text{m}}) * \text{B8:0.65}_{\mu\text{m_PAN}}$$

$$\text{BLUE} = \text{B2:0.56}_{\mu\text{m}} / (\text{B1:0.56}_{\mu\text{m}} + \text{B4:0.83}_{\mu\text{m}} + \text{B5:1.65}_{\mu\text{m}}) * \text{B8:0.65}_{\mu\text{m_PAN}}$$

Using the above band combination, the result is an image where all land features are sensibly enhanced. On the other hand, to achieve this, the Brovey transform clearly results in a radiometric change in the resultant image; this may not always be preferable when a further image classification is to be performed. Also, calculation needs to be carried out as a floating point, not as integer, to ensure precision is not lost. When applying this transform, an 11x11 sharpen filter on the high-resolution data normally exploits the final result at its best.

Digital imagery from high-relief or mountainous regions commonly embeds a radiometric distortion known as topographic effect. It is caused by the differences in illumination due to the angle of the sun during acquisition time and the angle between raypaths and terrain surface or slope (or, most notably, a combination of any landscape unit). This causes an alteration in image brightness values, resulting from (ERDAS, 1997):

- incident illumination (surface orientation with respect to raypath)
- exitance angle (amount of reflected energy as a function of the slope angle)
- surface cover characteristics (spatial extent and geometry of slopes)

One way to reduce topographic effect in the Landsat TM image herewith employed was by applying transformations based on either the Lambertian or Non-Lambertian reflectance models. These models perform topographic normalization, rendering the imagery as if it were a flat surface (ERDAS, 1997). The procedure needs:

- solar elevation and azimuth at time of image acquisition
- DEM file
- original imagery file (after atmospheric corrections)

The Non-Lambertian Reflectance model, herewith used, was initially studied in 1961 by Dr. Minnaert (ERDAS, 1997). It assumes that the surface does not reflect incident solar energy

uniformly in all directions. Taking into account terrain variations, it is certainly more computationally demanding but may provide with more accurate results. Its is computed via the following equation (ERDAS, 1997):

$$BV_{normal}^{\lambda} = \frac{BV_{observed}^{\lambda} \cdot \cos e}{\cos^k i \cdot \cos^k e}$$

where:

BV_{normal}^{λ}	= normalized brightness value
$BV_{observed}^{\lambda}$	= observed brightness value
$\cos i$	= cosine of incident angle
$\cos e$	= cosine of exitance angle (or slope angle)
k	= the empirically-derived Minnaert constant

k may be computed regressing a set of observed brightness values from the remotely-sensed imagery with known slope and aspect values, provided that all observation refer to the same type of land cover. The Minnaert constant is the slope of the regression line, obtained as follows (ERDAS, 1997 and references therein):

$$\log(BV_{observed}^{\lambda} \cdot \cos e) = \log BV_{normal}^{\lambda} + k \log(\cos i \cdot \cos e).$$

An example of the final, resulting TM image, equalized, re-transformed, topographically corrected and radiometrically enhanced is visible in **Fig. 3.20**.

3.4 Shaded relief

Shaded relief images provide an illustration of spatial variations in elevation across an area for which a DEM is known. Based on a relative position of a false sun (interactively decided by the analyst), areas that would be in sunlight are highlighted and areas that would be in shadow are thus shaded. Shade, therefore, is not intended as the one we ordinarily refer to, which is commonly cast by topographic features onto adjoining terrain after sunlight (**Fig. 3.21**).

Figure 3.20. RGB image of TM bands 4, 3, 2 (respectively) to highlight soil moisture and vegetation, in red. Band 4 embeds infrared information, capable of indicating relevant water content and generally humid environments. This clearly applies to paleochannels (image center and upper left) (data courtesy: IATA – CNR, Firenze).

For example, a prominent mountain with sun directed from NW would be illuminated in its NW side and shade rendered on its SE side; no shadow *towards* SE is simulated.

Figure 3.21. Shaded relief algorithm renders areas of a DEM whose computed slope is under direct virtual sun raypaths, while keeping in 'shadow' areas which are not. This does not entail a proper shadow to be cast from higher peaks onto lower ground, as we normally expect in nature (*redrawn, from: ERDAS, 1997*).

In calculating relief, ERDAS Imagine 8.3.1 routines compare the chosen sun position

and angles with the angle each pixel faces. The pixel is thus assigned a value V_p between -1 and $+1$ to indicate the amount of its specific light reflectance (ERDAS, 1997): $-1 \leq V_p \leq 0$ represent 'shadowed' areas, while $0 > V_p \geq +1$ indicate 'sunny' ones. These reflectance values are then applied to the original pixel values to obtain the final output.

ERDAS Imagine 8.3.1 sets all negative values to 0 or to the minimum light level defined. A co-registered image (i.e., a Landsat TM scene or an orthorectified airphoto) can be merged with a shaded relief images, in order to visually highlight specific terrain features associated with their light reflectance capability, irrespective of the terrain's radiometric properties. This can be very useful while concentrating on fault networks studied from DEM data but not immediately detectable from an airphoto with poor contrast. An example of this, to be best exploited further on (§ 4), can be observed in **Fig. 3.22**.

Figure 3.22. RGB image of bands 3,2,1 ('natural color') overlain onto shaded relief, false illuminated from NW (i.e., from a position not possible in nature). In the southern portion, notice WNW-ESE lineament trend highlighted by processing (*digital topography* © Regione Abruzzo; TM image courtesy IATA – CNR, Firenze).

3.5 Slope and aspect

In morphometric analysis, parameterization is the numerical description of continuous surface form (PIKE, 1993; ARGIALAS, 1995; GUTH, 1995; MCDERMID and FRANKLIN, 1995; WOOD, 1996). Since a polynomial function (of high order) can sensibly approximate and represent the main shifts in surface form (i.e., concavity, convexity and combinations thereof), main surface data can be described by various order of derivation of the following:

$$\frac{dz}{dxy} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial y}\right)^2}$$

being (x,y) the reference geographic position for a given pixel of z height. On the ground of the various order of derivation, the following parameters can be numerically constrained:

Morphometric attribute	Order of derivative
Elevation	0
Slope, aspect	1 st
Curvature	2 nd

Zero order derivatives describe entities directly inheritable from z, such as: average elevation, local relief, height frequency distribution, and hypsometric integral.

First order derivatives express slope trend and its predominant direction with respect to North. Slope (Fig. 3.23) is expressed as the change in elevation in function of the pixel's geometric resolution. It can be expressed in either percentage (the highest, the steepest) or in degrees, on the assumption that a slope of 45° = 100% (therefore, 90° = 200%). A 3x3 window is used to calculate slope at each pixel (ERDAS, 1997). For pixel e, of relative coordinates (x,y), the matrix is as follows:

a	b	c	$\Delta x_1 = c - a$	$\Delta y_1 = a - g$
d	e	f	$\Delta x_2 = f - d$	$\Delta y_2 = b - h$
g	h	i	$\Delta x_3 = i - g$	$\Delta y_3 = c - i$

hence,

$$\Delta x = \frac{(\Delta x_1 + \Delta x_2 + \Delta x_3)}{3 \cdot x_s} \qquad \Delta y = \frac{(\Delta y_1 + \Delta y_2 + \Delta y_3)}{3 \cdot y_s}$$

where x_s and y_s are x and y pixel size respectively. Finally:

Slope	Aspect
$\delta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{(\Delta x)^2 + (\Delta y)^2}}{2} \right) \cdot \frac{180}{\pi}$	$\Theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta y} \right)$

An aspect image (which was not employed for this research) is a gray-scale coded file according to the prevailing direction of the slope at each pixel (ERDAS, 1997). Aspect is

expressed in degrees from north, clockwise, from 0° to 360°. A value of 361° identifies flat

Figure 3.23. Slope map computed from the 1:10.000 sections of Carta Tecnica Regionale (*source contours* © Regione Abruzzo).

surfaces such as water bodies. Such files are generated using a 3x3 window around each pixel to calculate the prevailing direction it faces. For a given pixel P (x,y) with elevation values around it ranging $a-i$, average changes in elevation in both x and y directions are computed first (ERDAS, 1997).

Second order derivatives (by partial derivation) individuate the following morphometric features (after WOOD, 1996):

Feature name	Derivative expression	Description
Peak	$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2} > 0$ $\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial y^2} > 0$	Point that lies on a local convexity in all directions (all neighbors lower)
Ridge	$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2} > 0$ $\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial y^2} = 0$	Point that lies on a local convexity that is orthogonal to a line with no convexity/concavity
Pass	$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2} > 0$ $\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial y^2} < 0$	Point that lies on a local convexity that is orthogonal to a local concavity

Plane	$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2} = 0$	$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial y^2} = 0$	Points that do not lie on any surface concavity or convexity
Channel	$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2} < 0$	$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial y^2} = 0$	Point that lies on a local concavity that is orthogonal to a line with no convexity/concavity
Pit	$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2} < 0$	$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial y^2} < 0$	Point that lies on a local concavity in all directions (all neighbors higher)

It is critical to note that neither x nor y components need to be parallel to the DEM grid, since they lie in the direction of any maximum or minimum or steady height to be encountered within the 3x3 (a -> i) matrix (WOOD, 1996).

4. Quaternary geology and geomorphology

This research initially focused on the geomorphologic interpretation of the airphoto mosaic; the target was a detailed cartography of the Quaternary landforms and surface geology, to date available either (a) only for limited or (b) at the basin scale. The fine detail thence allowed to select regions of specific morphotectonic interest, primarily aimed at understanding what geomorphic impact is exerted by exogenous and endogenous constraints in a basin with limited and somewhat contradicting evidences.

4.1 The morphotectonic map

The main result from the geologic investigation of Campo Imperatore was conveyed into the production of a 1:10.000 geomorphological map (**Fig. 4.1**). Its main target was represented by landforms and their superposition across both time and space, whereas processes and their interferences were left for further investigation into chosen sub-regions, described in detail further on.

From a merely physiographic viewpoint and at a first glance, it is immediately evident that the basin is in fact two-fold. The Western portion, from the Mt. Aquila foothills to Mt. Mutri, is inscribed within a quasi-triangle shape, widening towards its SE border and itself being composed of two sectors, i.e. W and E of the N slope of Mt. S. Gregorio di Pagànica. The Eastern portion, from the outlet of Cortina Valley to Pietrattina and Cretarola towards SE, has a more regular shape, is dominated by remarkable alluvial bodies bearing equally significant erosional land sculpting. The overall basin's ground surface is generally dipping towards ESE, with a 32% gradient in the W portion and 55% in the E one. In fact, the general WNW-ESE strike also applies to almost any major fluvio-glacial landform and paleo-landsurface within the basin, thus suggesting that such condition has been predominant across a significant portion of the basin's life-cycle, clearly beyond present-day phenomena.

As far as the depositional systems are concerned, the Western half-area is characterized by:

- N strip: an array of small, entrenched and tight alluvial fans at the bottom of Mesozoic terranes upthrown by the border fault (S limb of Mt. Brancastello). Badlands and quarries developed on both bedrock and minor slope deposits;

- NW portion: V-shaped incised valleys of seasonal channeling sculpting a ‘cut&fill’ terrace system (Fontari and towards E);
- S/SE portion: frontal moraine ribbons developed either at the bottom of remarkable glacial cirques (N flank of Mt. Scinderella) or widespread amidst the basin (Coppe di S. Stefano), bearing intense karst effects and possible fracturing.

The Eastern portion of the basin rather hosts a conspicuous single alluvial fan system, with minor branches towards NE, is characterized by remarkable linear erosional features, both across the fan stack (Cocchiarelle) and through the deepest section (Cretarola).

Four main relief systems encircle and define the Campo Imperatore physiographic and depositional architecture:

- a) Gran Sasso Range - from Mt. Aquila (NW) to Mt. Guardiola (SE), its S flank represents the N shoulder that frames half of the overall basin. It has been downthrown by the Campo Imperatore normal border fault, at least in its E-W branch. The fault then acts as the (Northern) major interface between bedrock and Quaternary deposits;
- b) Mt. Scindarella – it imposes a sharp constraint to the development of the NW valley system, thus (1) actually splitting the W portion of Campo Imperatore in two sub-regions and (2) hosting the development of glacial cirques entirely within the basin, which acted as main sources for extensive moraine deposition;
- c) Mt. Bolza – together with a wide Mesozoic limestone strip on its NE foothills, it marks the S/SE shoulder of the Eastern sub-basin;
- d) Mt. Paradiso – this in fact splits Campo Imperatore into the two distinct basins and, as will be discussed further on, also provides with critical hints as to the bedrock/alluvium arrangement.

Dataset for this research, although essentially aimed at the Quaternary basin, also covers its S margin. It primarily consists of bedrock antiformals displaced by normal fault systems, the latter present in 3 main families:

- (1) NW-SE, SW-verging, very high relief, loosely spaced (at least in the W portion of the margin), whose geomorphic expression is highlighted by strata surfaces and rinnenkarren;
- (2) WNW-ESE, NNE-verging, low relief, closely spaced, mostly revealed by

Morphotectonic signature of the Campo Imperatore Quaternary basin (Central Apennines): implications for the seismotectonics of Central Italy

Morphotectonic map, Campo Imperatore (Central Italy)

Umberto Fracassi
Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra
Università degli Studi di Firenze
Italy

LEGEND

- Active drainage
- Abandoned or seasonal drainage
- Active fan
- Recent fan
- Abandoned fan
- Doline field (on pre-Q bedrock)
- Doline field (on Q moraines)
- Glacial cirque
- Quarrying, badlands
- Scarp
- Aligned sinkholes, rinnenkarren
- Karst saddles, polje
- Colluvium
- Stratal surface
- Structural surface
- Terrace (I° order)
- Terrace (II° order)
- Terrace (III° order)
- Normal fault, uncertain fault
- Lineament

Topographic basis 1:10000 © Regione Abruzzo

Figure 4.1

structural surfaces, and

- (3) ENE-WSW, of various geometries, low relief, loosely spaced, sometimes expressed by structural surfaces.

This upland region is dominated by extensive karst systems, primarily poljes, normally bounded by adjoining normal fault systems, endorheic patches, and aligned sinkholes along normal fault traces. It is important to stress that karst is a prevailing and active geomorphic factor in this region, as it is not uncommon in intermontane basins of Central Italy. In summary, apart from the N border of the basin itself, clearly dominated by alluvial fan deposition, virtually every other landform was influenced, triggered when not caused, by various degrees of karst processes, either at some stage or along its entire development, either on the mere surface or through a conspicuous section, both on alluvium and on pre-Quaternary bedrock. Approximately one third of the overall investigated area (i.e. the basin and its mountain environs) hosts karst-induced landforms, whereas the area again is a karst system in its entirety (Fig. 4.2), also within and below the moraine systems.

Figure 4.2. The comprehensive karst system: a composite diagram illustrating the major phenomena encountered in active karst terrains (redrawn, from: FORD and WILLIAMS, 1989).

With the above guidelines, we can now concentrate on sub-areas of the basin which retain specific interest and importance to best highlight those geomorphic processes which contributed to the present-day arrangement of Campo Imperatore. Given the basin's setup, to maintain a geographic and morphological inner consistency through the following description, we will start from the uppermost features, to be found at the NW tip of the

overall area, thence proceeding towards SE to underline geomorphic scenarios that are meaningful as we gather sequential knowledge.

4.2 Constraints exerted by the border faults

The E slope of Mt. Brancastello, apart from a minor ENE-verging glacial cirque on its top, is actually a sharp structural surface due to a fault separating Mt. Scindarella on the E from the floodplain. At the bottom of the triangular facet no sedimentation is to be found. Since a source for this exists (the breached slope), either such deposits were (and are) washed away from seasonal runoff or they underwent karst dissolution. While the former hypothesis would be partially supported by the fault's NNW-ESE strike, compatible with principal flowpaths in this restricted section of the basin, the latter stands out as piping and soffusion is a major geomorphic factor on the Coppe di S. Stefano moraines, a few hundreds m to the E. Also, this scenario is very common on the S margin of Campo Imperatore, where virtually no fan system is emplaced at the bottom of reliefs. The geometry of the invoked fault is unclear; its trace does not appear to cut into the Gran Sasso Range, only 1.5 km to the N, while the fault exerts a geomorphic expression for ~ 8 km towards SE, possibly due to differential erosion. Its strike, the overall arrangement of the basin and the unlikely abrupt tip towards NE would envisage a strike-slip dextral kinematics but this is not yet proved due to paucity of outcrops along its inferred trace.

Where, conversely, a known fault deforms known terranes is on the contact between Mt. Prena and Le Veticole, on the S limb of the Gran Sasso Range (**Fig. 4.3**). A branch of the Campo Imperatore border fault cuts through Entrochi Calcarenites (Malm – Dogger) and Fucoia Marls Fm. (Aptian – Lower Cenomanian; VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998), thus separating the primary mountain front from its hanging-wall. Activity of this fault and its relationship with the basin is debated but it certainly marked a physiographic threshold, as far as slope morphology is concerned here. The S flank of Mt. Prena is a whole bedrock outcrop, revealing a chaotic geology as resulting from imbricate thrusting, with a rough slope surface, hosting remarkable badlands and quarries. The inner limb of Le Veticole, conversely, shows only patches of discernible bedding, interspersed among remnants of pentagonal facets and high-angle colluvium.

Figure 4.3. Splay of the Campo Imperatore normal border fault, cutting through bedrock limestone. Notice the remarkable difference in gullying and quarrying between hanging-wall and footwall.

4.3 Glacial forms and deposits

Glacial processes exerted sharp morpho-sculpting in the topographically highest portion of the basin, the N flank of Mt. Scindarella (**Fig. 4.4**), about 1.5 km to SE from the previous spot. Three major glacial cirques, ascribed to the last glaciation pulse in Campo Imperatore (**Table 4.1**; JAURAND, 1998), were excavated onto thrust Mesozoic terranes. A conspicuous landmass was perched out of the mountain front, in part redeposited at its basal slope and within the glacial amphitheaters; likely, it also significantly contributed to outer moraine fronts well away in the central basin. Frontal moraine ribbons have a remarkable physiographic expression, as the coarse material (from the calcirudites of the Scaglia Rossa Fm.; GHISSETTI and VEZZANI, 1990) accumulated on the foreslope and onto

Figure 4.4. Glacial cirque system on the N limb of Mt. Scindarella, in the NW sector of Campo Imperatore. This area and, secondarily, Mt. Aquila (~ 1 km towards W) are the only locations within the basin displaying intense development of glacial forms with such magnitude. At the base of this glacially-eroded slope, conspicuous basal moraines and their frontal ribbons accumulated, later to be subject to (a) stagnant ice modeling and (b) intense karst piping and dolines together with bedrock (where outcropping at the base of the slope).

bedrock outcrops. The resulting basal slope is a single prominent ribbon, downbroken by substratum remnants. The overall front underwent significant piping, as is documented by the doline field that developed irrespective of stratigraphy, thus indicating that karst processes here are subsequent to moraine emplacement. This is an important consideration that will be needed as we describe karst terranes towards SE, their inherited morphology and relative timing of dissolution inception.

Relative chronology	N-wards permanent snow level (after maximum Würm expansion)	Principal moraines ascribable to each glacial pulse (with altitude of corresponding front)	Evolution of glaciation
Maximum expansion of recent Würm (~ 19 ka B.P.)	1756 m	CI: Coppe di S. Stefano (1590 m); VV: (1165 m)	Alpine-type, over a 70 km ² total surface. Four composite glaciers 5-10 km long.
Apenninic Stage I	1810 m (+ 54 m)	CI: Piano Pietranzoni (1640 m); AV: Arno point (1150 m)	Slight front retreat (1/2 km) for large composite glaciers. Halved surface of Campo Imperatore glacier
Apenninic Stage IIa	2030 m (+ 274 m)	CI: base of Mt. Scindarella (1750 - 1850 m), Mt. Fontari (1925 - 2050 m); AV: Maone Valley (1700 m); CV (1930 m)	End of main confluences. Retreat of large glaciers in uplands. End of numerous S-wards cirque glaciers.
Apenninic Stage IIb	2149 m (+ 393 m)	CI: cirques of Mt. Scindarella (1950 - 2000 m) and of Mt. Aquila (2200 m); AV and VV: upper (1920 - 1950 m)	Shredding of Campo Imperatore main glacier into multiple, isolated bodies. Some glaciers remain on the N flank of the Gran Sasso chain (max 1.5 km)
Apenninic Stage III	2314 m (+ 558 m)	AV and VV: uppermost cirques (2050 - 2200 m); MP: Northern slope (2200 m)	Glaciation entirely disappears from Campo Imperatore. Cornacchie Valley hosts the only glacier remnant, plus some minor ones on highest cirques of Gran Sasso.

Table 4.1. Late-Würm evolution of glaciers within and surrounding Campo Imperatore. **CI:** Campo Imperatore; **VV:** Venacquaro Valley; **AV:** Arno Valley; **CV:** Chiarino Valley; **MP:** Mt. Prena (*after: JAURAND, 1998*).

Towards the E margin of this portion of Campo Imperatore, few whaleback remnants of depositional paleo-landsurfaces recorded the extent of glacial deposits beyond moraine ribbons (JAURAND, 1998; KOTARBA et al., 2001) and the subsequent landsculpting. Piano Racollo (**Fig. 4.5**) is the lowermost area W of Mt. Paradiso and marks a succession of erosional and depositional events that will be highlighted in greater detail further on, as additional data will be discussed (§ 7.3). The alignment Mt. Paradiso – Mt. Bolza displays bedrock reliefs that underwent considerable SW-verging normal faulting. This boundary constrained the basin, trapping an alluvial fan system originating from the foothills of Mt. Prena, which was later cut (**Fig. 4.6**) toward its toe. This left a few whaleback remnants separated by wide channels, to N away from the fan and to S from bedrock. Such channeling was in fact conveyed towards E into Cortina Valley (see further on). Proofs of

Figure 4.5. Photostrip depicting transition from the thrustbelt foothills (N) to the Piano Racollo plain, W of the Cortina Valley intermediate erosional threshold, with a prominent terrace remnant on the foreground. The latter’s visual reconstruction is widened by photographs superposition (out of scale).

such “cut & fill” terrace system are underlined by the sharp scarp cutting the alluvial body and by other minor erosional inner edges within the overall plain of Piano Racollo.

Figure 4.6. Remnants of the glacial regimes within central Campo Imperatore as “cut&fill” sculpted paleo-landsurfaces (redrawn, from: JAURAND, 1998).

4.4 Terracing and geomorphic thresholds

As previously introduced, the large portion W of Mt. Paradiso displays the largest and most articulate depositional features, to be inscribed within the upper and lower sectors. On the S foothills of Mt. Aquila, where a major glacial cirque was carved, a two-fold terrace system developed within the Fontari area (Fig. 4.7). Sharp badlands were excavated across

the Mesozoic bedrock and, secondarily, on moderate slope deposits; from these, an array of seasonal fluvio-glacial channels perched the paleo-landsurfaces. Channeling shows remarkable V-shaped valley profiles; its outflows is thence captured by a major linear erosional system, parallel to the mountain front, again with marked V-shaped valley profiles.

Figure 4.7. Paired perched terraces in the Fontari slopes (uppermost sector of the NW portion of Campo Imperatore). Seasonal erosion across the upper terrace slope is in part characterized by V-shaped valley profiles transversal to the scarp. Such evidence suggests a steady and fast relative uplift. Also subsequent erosion on the main valley floor explicits sharp and V-shaped incision profiles (parallel to photo frame).

The latter developed onto the lower terrace and, given their sharp transversal profiles, morpho-logically consistent with channeling across the scarp of the upper surface, they hint at a substantial lowering of the base level, an evidence to be found virtually all over the area of study. At close-range, it is unclear whether the paired terraces are due to a “cut & fill” arrangement (photo inset and **Fig. 4.8**) or they resulted from a flat valley perched through the initial alluvial stack; nevertheless, zooming out from the spot, the lower

paleosurface can be uniformly followed well ahead into the almost flat floodplain (see indicating the latter is actually caused by a second depositional event subsequent to valley excavation. Such landsculpting may prospectively be correlated to moraine systems to be found later on in the central sector of Campo Imperatore.

Environment	Terrain	Process	Terrace type
RANGES	Bedrock	Lateral bevelling and subsequent vertical incision	STRATH
BASINS	Plio-Quaternary continental deposits	Valley filling and subsequent vertical incision	FILL
		Valley filling and subsequent episodic incision	CUT

Figure 4.8. Sketch simplifying the terrace sets that develop within continental environments in the Central Apennines, as related to their causative geomorphic process and the associated lithotypes (redrawn, from: BASILI, 1999).

The last glaciation redeposited material on the previously carved glacio-fluvial Rionne system, through the incision of Cortina Valley. Such feature perched onto both alluvium and, towards E, onto bedrock, where it cuts through a gorge in the Scoppaturo area (**Fig. 4.9**). Scoppaturo in fact represents the E termination of Cortina Valley s.s. This sharp-edged valley, through the tectonic contact between Fucoida Marls (Cenomanian – Aptian) and Miocene terranes (VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998), developed a V-shaped transversal profile until the bend towards S. From this point onwards, landsculpting deeply excavated through Mesozoic bedrock, perching a meandering canyon towards E.

The sharp landsculpting that perches through bedrock from Scoppaturo onwards also cut the southernmost alluvium of Campo Imperatore, directed through Piano dell’Ospedale (**Fig. 4.10**). This sedimentary body is bounded to W by a sharp, aligned contact with the Calcare Massiccio Fm. (Sinemurian – Hettangian; VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998), itself carved by W-E channeling that perched through bedrock. A very large V-shaped valley cuts

through alluvium and was perched contemporaneously with the

Figure 4.9. Perched landscape at the E tip of Cortina Valley, connecting alluvium from Piano Racollo with the E portion of Campo Imperatore. Bedrock terranes, that underwent extensive reverse and normal faulting and, afterwards, intense karst processes, have been dissected by regressive erosion from E, thus leaving room for a subsequent depositional body. This, in turn, was affected by inner karst conduits, as suggested by the absence of any basal slope accumulation.

canyon developed onto bedrock, as suggested by its morphological continuity throughout. As was the case for Cortina Valley, both canyon and present-day valley were refilled; currently, a seasonal flowpath meanders through the wide valley floor. At least three paleo-landsurfaces are recognizable, interpreted as a possible superposition of erosional and depositional tops of a “cut&fill” system (**Fig. 4.11**). Widespread erosion is demonstrated by relict valleys, suspended river banks hinting at a large meandering system, reworked and downcut terrace scarps, paleoflow due to tributaries from the bedrock slope. All such features refer to a stage when the landscape was centered on the uppermost flat surface and no major valley could have been excavated. This can be inferred by maximum dip paleo-

directions.

Figure 4.10. Overview of the “cut&fill” terrace system bounding the depositional body of Piano dell’Ospedale, the topographically lowest portion within the Campo Imperatore floodplain. A flooded valley incised a remarkable alluvial system; both alluvium and, ultimately, seasonal stream were controlled by the downslope Upper Tavo reach. At least three erosional stages were discriminated, recorded by resulting paleo-landsurfaces.

The sharp trace that borders Piano dell’Ospedale reveals a pre-existing fault that displaced the Calcare Massiccio prior to juxtaposition of alluvium. Its distinct contact was underlined by preferential lateral erosion, triggered by hard-rock morphoselection. This is indicated by the inner edge of the uppermost erosional surface that bends towards SE, perched the bedrock sideways and then gently bends again towards E. Deepening of base level may have thence caused incision of the central channel, which then led to the genesis of the present-day valley.

Campo Imperatore underwent various stages of dissection, as indicated by the array of erosional thresholds identified towards its SE margin (**Fig. 4.12**). The Tavo River upper reach breached through the thrustbelt SE limb (SW of Mt. Guardiola), likely underlining the role of lowering base level in an area undergoing regional uplift, possibly to be connected with the advancing thrust front underneath the eastern foothills of the Gran Sasso Range (BASILI, 1999). From a digital topographic profile across the geomorphic

Figure 4.11. 3D block diagram showing bedrock-alluvium interface in Piano dell’Ospedale, the SE (lowest) portion of the Campo Imperatore floodplain and erosional features inherited in the terrace stack. The latter was sculpted by the Tavolo River upper reach (now inactive). The normal fault terminating the Jurassic limestone does not cut through the sedimentary cover. Its sharp trace and its NW-SE strike (see airphoto close-up) suggest recent morphoselection induced by channelling on the uppermost paleo-landsurface (topographic data courtesy IRTR-CNR, © Regione Abruzzo).

expression of such thresholds, a relative timing is suggested by different degrees of land-sculpting. This information is thence substantiated by a radial CW shift in the paleoflow paths perched by channeling dissecting La Fossa (to the E) and the large Cocchiarelle alluvial system (towards W). This evidence may suggest that the E/NE shoulder of the Gran

Figure 4.12. Clockwise rotation of threshold activity. Most recently active one (Cretarola) also exerted piracy on secondary flow from NNW (Piano dell'Ospedale). Threshold rotational shift and recent flow, gradually pressing Mt. Bolza carbonate N foothills, together suggest uplift on the N/NE flank of the Gran Sasso chain (*orthorectified airphoto mosaic overlain onto 230m grid Digital Elevation Model. Airphotos © Istituto Geografico Militare, courtesy of INGV; DEM is provided by Servizio Geologico d'Italia*).

Sasso Range is being uplifted and/or that maximum dip direction in this portion of Campo Imperatore undergoes sensible active modification. As is the case with the entrenched alluvial stack studied on the S foothills of Mt. Brancastello, shifts in flowpaths represent a critical information to be fully exploited further on in this work.

4.5 Alluvial fans and channeling systems

The Rionne – La Canala fan (**Fig. 4.13**) is one of the widest and best developed alluvial system within Campo Imperatore. Between the foreslopes of the Le Veticole – Mt. Faeto's remarkable triangular facets and W of Mt. Paradiso – Mt. Mutri, a widespread two-fold asymmetric alluvial system partially circumscribes Mt. Paradiso and widens towards S, well into Piano Racollo. It consists of three main stages:

- 1) Upper Pleistocene alluvial stack, ~ 10 m thick, underlying the entire system. Its S

toe was cut by the incision of Cortina Valley (see further on and § 7.2) and now shows 3 (possibly 4) normal surface fractures, ~ 500 m long and likewise spaced, < 2 m throw, with a gentle scarp modeled as a transport-limited surface (ARROWSMITH et al., 1986; HILLEY et al., 2001 – *subm.*). None of these features ruptures through the adjoining Mt. Paradiso bedrock.

- II) Upper Pleistocene – Holocene aprons, gradually aggradational towards SW, clockwise shifting from S-ward deposition. Lowermost aprons seal the geomorphic expression of the above fractures. These were carved by subsequent incision, both laterally and on the very surface. In the first case, modeling followed a S-ward outwash from the main channel, whereas the second developed via rills and gullies that followed the new maximum dip direction (a shift of ~ 30° W-ward). Recent aprons also deposited towards W, resulting from intermittent outer washes of the main feeding channel.
- III) Present-day main source channel, re-excavating the overall stack. It cuts through the entire section, from the bedrock outcrop to the final outwash in the Piano Racollo plain. It perches Mesozoic terranes right across a relay ramp, highlighted by (a) differential erosion of hard-rock and (b) displacement overlap and overstep. It then sharply carves its straight thalweg and, eventually, bends towards S (a feature already well seen in previous fan systems a few km NW from Rionne).

CW shift of linear erosion visibly occurs on both sides of the major channel and is probably due to the sensible thickening of the overall stack and its mound-shaped transversal profile, as modeled elsewhere by FIELD (2001) and RITTER et al. (2000). Towards the S toe, a W-E trending channel excavated part of the lowermost unit, possibly in accordance with the development of the Piano Racollo Glaciation (KOTARBA et al., 2001).

The only place where noticeable surface rupture occurred on the Quaternary cover is the one just described, and with the evident geometric constraints imposed by the short traces, if compared to the significant Campo Imperatore border fault. Nevertheless, this evidence also highlights their co-linearity with long-traced structures (of uncertain vergence) to be found across the SE margin of the basin, predominantly on Calcare Massiccio Fm.

Figure 4.13. Late Quaternary fractures on Rionne - La Canala alluvial fan. Notice interferences of fan development with surface runoff pattern and relative timing of faulting vs. final stages of apron deposition (airphotos courtesy INGV, © Istituto Geografico Militare Italiano).

(Hettangian – Sinemurian; VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998). In fact, an array of N120° and, secondarily, N80° faults criss-cross over bedrock (**Fig. 4.14**). Their presence is underlined by rinnenkarren aligned along fault traces. Karst imprint on bedrock is an important constrain to the geomorphic expression of such traces, in as much as piping, inception of doline fields and dissolution tend to smooth the effects of local displacement away. However, there is no continuity between fracturing found across bedrock and those detected on the lowermost fan lobe. Therefore, a non-tectonic origin for these minor structures is reasonable, as already observed in similar contexts (ORNDORFF and SOUTHWORTH, 1997; MACHETTE et al., 1998). Differential compaction may have triggered surface accommodation of a 10/15 m thick alluvium stack, also considering that the Rionne fan developed onto a pre-karst landscape.

Figure 4.14. La Canala - Rionne alluvial fan, adjoining Mt. Paradiso and the Mesozoic faulted terranes. Most structures trend WNW-ESE, including the small fractures encountered across the fan. None ruptures throughout the overall area, irrespective of the terrane involved, as the above faulting is pre-existing to the alluvium, which likely accommodated its thin cover by differential compaction upon the underlying structures (*Airphotos © Istituto Geografico Militare, courtesy of INGV*).

4.6 Ancient and active flowpaths of sediment dispersal

NE from Scoppaturo, back on the floodplain, we enter the Eastern portion of Campo Imperatore. Cocchiarelle (**Fig. 4.15**), the largest alluvial system in the basin, accounts for an elongated thick body, with an array of subsequent aprons and shields. A few observations are critical:

- 1) we are in a topographically lower section, displaying a large fan stack which does not seem to bear lateral reworking (as it is, conversely, common around the numerous fans in the W portion), i.e. the depositional history of the lowermost apron seems not to have been interrupted by factors that could constrain its spatial development;
- 2) a two-fold channel system, with smoothed V-shaped transversal profiles, terraced the lowermost fan lobe and was then partly refilled. This channeling deeply carved the overall fan and, as often occurs in Campo Imperatore for recent geomorphic features, it trends N120°, thus indicating a former maximum dip direction;
- 3) such strike is to be considered former here in as much as present-day channeling is excavating the S foothills of Mt. Camicia virtually N-S. A relevant fraction of fine material is in fact being transported via the above formerly-carved channels (toward SE), but main sediment load, also inclusive of large boulders, is conveyed towards S.

From a drainage viewpoint, it is important to notice that present-day maximum dip direction forces active channeling to carve the fan stack across its topographic top, i.e. the less favorable condition unless either (a) a significant kinetic energy sustains such massive transport across a critical gradient or (b) the overall alluvial system (and its conterminous terrain) is being tilted S-ward or (c) major drainage across the basin is capturing flowpath from Mt. Camicia. Indeed:

- 1) active sedimentation is conveyed towards channeling carved into bedrock from Scoppaturo (towards E) and
- 2) to reach such bedrock carving, active channeling breached a morphological threshold opposed by the Cocchiare Fault (CARRARO and GIARDINO, 1992) and, therefore, was not diverted and captured by the fault limb.

Figure 4.15. Cocchiarelle - La Fossa fan. This is the widest-reaching alluvial system within Campo Imperatore, showing a CCW shift in degree of activity among channeling. While channel and levees in a fan tend to migrate for depositional geometries, the largest N-S one is cutting upslope (i.e., in opposition to the morphological norm). Its kinetic energy, already proportional to the remarkable system, allows the new channel to breach a bedrock threshold (*Airphotos © Istituto Geografico Militare, courtesy of INGV*).

Mt. Brancastello displays a long and continuous SW-verging front, facing Mt. Scindarella N flank. This slope is dominated by an array of entrenched alluvial fans (**Fig. 4.16**), of small extent if compared to other very prominent examples towards the center of the basin and farther E. A possible reason for their limited setup may be simply due to lack of sufficient horizontal accommodation space away from the front, constrained by the E tip of Mt. S. Gregorio di Pagànica. Another possibility is that linear incision from the very NW tip of Campo Imperatore was (and still is) competitor with fan development, thus washing away episodic deposition from Mt. Brancastello. Nevertheless, active branches of present-day fan systems are all generally trending towards S, i.e. about 30° S from maximum dip direction for this mountain front; such feature is in fact noticeable over most fan systems in Campo Imperatore. It is herewith useful to stress that all of these systems are S-verging, i.e. originating only from the N margin of the basin, although the Gran Sasso Range does not include all significant reliefs bounding the research area. Therefore, we may infer that the

Figure 4.16. CW radial shift in channel activity. Rilling rotates towards N, while fresh fan sedimentation switches towards S. Notice how fan toes are reworked by WNW-ESE lead channel. Underlying fan lobes developed towards SW, i.e. orthogonal to slope. The two geomorphic evidences do not contrast one another, as uplift in the Gran Sasso Range bedrock shoulder causes present-day seasonal drainage and fan deposits to be conveyed towards S (Airphotos © Istituto Geografico Militare, courtesy of INGV).

process responsible for the morphogenesis of the S flank of Mt. Brancastello is different from the one which is triggering present-day sedimentation at its bedrock/Quaternary interface.

Sharp carving of the Cortina Valley and the canyon behind is in fact responsible for an overall steep-sided channeling through the entire Campo Imperatore (**Fig. 4.17**). Profiles of thalweg and adjoining topographic swath from Piano Pietranzoni to Piano dell'Ospedale reveal that:

- a) gradient of thalweg is generally consistent from NW to SE, partially flattened in Cortina Valley. Its profile runs 'above' topography in Piano Racollo, which in fact is where no stream occurs, as this channel starts from the foreslope of Mt. Brancastello, runs through the doline field of Coppe di S. Stefano but then disappears in a blind valley on exiting these outer moraines;
- b) differential between topography and thalweg highlights the incoherent surface of Coppe di S. Stefano, the sharp contribution due to bedrock around Mt. Mutri –

- Scoppaturo and the rough terrain represented by rinnenkarren and aligned sinkholes modeled through the Calcare Massiccio Fm.;
- c) remarkable peaks in thalweg slope, from Scoppaturo towards E, suggest that the canyon, although partially refilled and bevelled, inherits a landscape already modeled by karst systems. In Piano dell’Ospedale, terracing affected also the valley floor at a late stage, witnessed by sensible scarps.

Figure 4.17. Profiles of geomorphometric measurements along thalweg of seasonal drainage across the entire Campo Imperatore basin. Notice passage from alluvium to bedrock around the Mt. Paradiso - Cortina Valley threshold, whose sharp differential highlights passage from the karst-dominated plain of Piano Racollo to the gorge sculpted into the Mesozoic faulted limestone.

4.7 Erosional and depositional systems: and deformation?

A general perspective (**Fig. 4.18**) of landforms and their extent in Campo Imperatore underlines two seemingly diverging landscape scenarios:

- 1) low-relief ancient forms, such as the major alluvial bottom lobes and remarkable abandoned channels, generally reflect a smooth geomorphic evolution, in both geometric and spatial accordance with the post-contractual architecture of this basin. No direct evidence of surface deformation is fully discernible on this setup, apart from minor and very short fractures atop the Pleistocene lobe of the Rionne – La Canala fan system. Depositional systems developed in an already deformed tectonic environment;
- 2) recent and active forms seem to reflect effects of S-ward tilting of the surrounding Gran Sasso Range, thus carving a new glaci-fluvial pattern. Erosion is a key threshold, beyond which remarkable channeling perches onto the pre-existing landscape, either on bedrock or on alluvium. River terracing is thus a leveling factor to frame the modern floodplain, where linear erosion shifts from inherited flowpaths to fresh directions recognizable at the basin scale.

Stratigraphic contact between the lowest units of the Quaternary infill and bedrock does not outcrop. This implies that thickness of the alluvial cover cannot be directly evaluated from observable geology. Notwithstanding, since vertical erosion exerted an intense geomorphic impact on the sedimentary units if compared to their spatial extent, the thickness of the Campo Imperatore soft cover may not be insignificant or, at least, it could display an uneven distribution across the basin. We noticed that Cortina Valley perched through both bedrock and alluvium and that its activity is genetically related to canyon escarpment and valley floor, up to Piano dell’Ospedale. Therefore, since the two erosional systems are connected and since Piano dell’Ospedale is the topographical lowest sector of the overall basin, thus receiving the entire flowpath, it is possible that the sedimentary stack thickens towards SE.

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Figure 4.18. Geomorphic expression of tectonic provinces within the basin and their likely interplay with sediment dispersal pattern (Dataset is a merger of shaded relief DEM; 10m contours courtesy of IRTR - CNR, © Regione Abruzzo, and of 30m Landsat TM image, courtesy of IATA - CNR).

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In summary, we observed two distinct groups of physiographic units, W and E of Mt. Paradise, that could also prove to be separate depositional arrangements, thus introducing the fact that Campo Imperatore is not a single fault-bounded – or fault-generated – basin but, rather, consists of two basins apart, connected only by erosional systems at the range scale. This information, if proved, would rewrite assumptions and views about the syn-

tectonic nature of this basin (GIRAUDI, 1994; D'AGOSTINO et al., 1997; D'AGOSTINO et al., 1998; KOTARBA et al., 2001) and would, therefore, underline the importance of geomorphological investigation to support either model.

Consequently, information about the basin's thickness is needed to ascertain its vertical architecture, so as to better constrain relative timing of deposition and its relationship with structures that mark the boundary between hard-rock and soft cover. Considering that present deformation, if proved, offers an uncertain and scatter picture in Campo Imperatore and that surface ruptures are very isolated if compared to the major normal structures, the next chapter of this work aims at filling this knowledge gap.

5. Bedrock: geophysical prospecting

To measure distance between the ground surface and the bedrock/infill interface, a relatively simple method was applied, already successfully employed in similar geologic scenarios by other Authors. The sampling technique is feasible with fairly small commitment, both financial and logistical. Results can then be processed with available computing resources.

5.1 Environmental microtremors

Seismic noise (IBS VON-SEHT and WOHLBERG, 1999) defines ground vibrations due to neither earthquakes nor explosions and that are strictly pertinent to a given site, since they are not caused by a remote and/or larger source. Recent research (DELGADO et al., 2000; YUNCHA and LUZÓN, 2000; ALBARELLO, 2001; SATOH et al., 2001; VIGNOLA, 2001) demonstrated that, given a sedimentary basin with a soft layer overlying a hard bedrock, such microseismicity allows to infer depth of bedrock/cover interface discriminating horizontal from vertical motion components, thus isolating their spectral ratio (HVSr Nakamura's technique).

The system, initially devised by Dr. Nakamura for roadwork prospecting along the Japanese rail tracks, has been successfully applied by the above Authors (among the many others) to soft cover in recent depocenters with a presumably thin loose cover. This procedure assumes the following:

- microtremors are due to local sources;
- sources of microtremors on the ground do not interfere with microtremors at the layer bottom;
- vertical component is not enhanced by the soft cover;
- function maxima indicate resonance frequencies of soft cover for S waves.

Therefore, the ratio between vertical motion components on the surface V_S and on the bottom V_B embeds mere local sources at the surface $A_S(v)$ and on the bottom $A_B(v)$:

$$R_V(v) = \frac{V_S(v)}{V_B(v)} = \frac{A_S(v)}{A_B(v)}$$

The ratio between amplitude of the horizontal spectrum component on the surface H_S and at the bottom H_B inherits both source and site amplification input $S_S(\nu)$:

$$R_H(\nu) = \frac{H_S(\nu)}{H_B(\nu)} = \frac{A_S(\nu)}{A_B(\nu)} \cdot S_S(\nu)$$

Computing the ratio between $R_H(\nu)$ and $R_V(\nu)$, the site transfer function is obtained:

$$\frac{R_H(\nu)}{R_V(\nu)} = \frac{H_S(\nu)}{H_B(\nu)} \cdot \frac{V_B(\nu)}{V_S(\nu)} = S_S(\nu)$$

Assuming that, at the soft cover bottom and for all resonance frequencies seeked:

$$\frac{H_B(\nu)}{V_B(\nu)} = 1 \quad \text{then:} \quad S(\nu) = \frac{H_S(\nu)}{V_S(\nu)}$$

to calculate sediment/bedrock interface:

$$d = \frac{V_S}{4\nu}$$

where:

- d = sediment thickness
- ν = resonance frequency for a single uniform layer
- V_S = velocity of Rayleigh waves

The latter is assumed constant, which can clearly introduce evaluation errors in as much as a sedimentary cover, however recent and thin, could not be imagined homogeneous; IBS VON-SEHT and WOHLBERG (1999) therefore introduced a gradient in the computation. For each site, the most significant values were chosen within the 0.1 – 10 Hz range. The peak representing the maximum amplification achieved was considered the lead value to calculate sediment thickness.

Measurements, with coordinates taken within the UTM map projection, were conducted in 59 sites located within the boundary of the Quaternary/bedrock interface on the ground surface (**Fig. 5.1**). They were evenly spaced across the basin borders, each station within a ~ 700/800 m range from each other. Sites were clearly identified from known geology and previous fieldwork, thus concentrating on the most dubious spots

Figure 5.1. Position of the 59 HVSR mobile stations (as per Nakamura's method, 1989), with respect to (a) major normal faults, (b) position of main thrust sheet and (c) stratigraphic contact between Quaternary cover and bedrock. Additional points, digitized at the bedrock-alluvium contact throughout, were computed assuming zero basin depth, so as to make the dataset self-consistent. Faults are in part derived from published geological cartography at 1:100.000 (topographic basemap: 1:25.000 © Istituto Geografico Militare Italiano).

(where reachable). Nevertheless, the Western sector of Campo Imperatore sometimes required extensive off-road driving beyond the actual automotive limits. Specifically, the instrument needed to be permanently connected to the car battery charger, which prevented from data recording in remote areas where driving was not possible with available resources. The whole geophysical campaign was organized with Prof. Marco Mucciarelli and handled with Angela Santomassimo (both from Università della Basilicata).

Further 53 points were added on the very border of the Quaternary basin, so as to obtain points in which no microtremor measurements were needed since bedrock was outcropping. These ‘zero depth’ points had a two-fold goal: (a) a constraint to inscribe the dataset within known geological boundaries and (b) a cross-reference to test data reliability, since zero depth could be geometrically assumed via bedrock outcrop.

Finally, 44 points were added from outside the basin boundary, i.e. from upland bedrock. Such data, while being again at ‘zero depth’, were chosen to fully circumscribe the dataset within a region that underwent carving. This implies that a morphological consistency is expected between the underlying interface and the outlying bedrock flanks.

5.2 Thickness vs. depositional systems

For each of the 59 stations, 5 measures were actually taken, employing one minute each for data gathering; the processing algorithms require at least 3 valid measures per site. From the above site measurements, processing (performed at Università della Basilicata) computed a best fit for 35 of the above data points, thus improving spectral resolution but somewhat reducing the spatial one. Such sub-sampling, however, was as evenly spaced across the available grid as the original stations were. **Table 5.1** illustrates the obtained values.

Depth of bedrock interface was computed as follows:

$$d = SE - \frac{250}{4v}$$

where SE is site elevation and 250 is a constant velocity value of S -waves for the average type of soft-cover investigated.

Eastings	Northings	Averaged v	Site elevation	MT isopach	Thickness Q
384090,0089	4700748,446	1	1840	1777,5	62,5
387749,5966	4695883,722	1	1660	1597,5	62,5
389595,0294	4695204,564	1	1584	1521,5	62,5
390343,6378	4695067,269	1	1573	1510,5	62,5
391439,0328	4694994,63	1	1558	1495,5	62,5
396810,3592	4695378,6	1	1495	1432,5	62,5
395564,2	4697090,859	1	1564	1501,5	62,5
393596,4747	4696062,107	1	1599	1536,5	62,5
386854,5884	4698306,156	1,259	1647	1597,4	49,6
386129,3706	4699146,535	1,259	1667	1617,4	49,6
396860,0113	4694671,5	1,259	1488	1438,4	49,6
395767,07	4696071,583	1,259	1543	1493,4	49,6
394805,4031	4696596,901	1,259	1602	1552,4	49,6
394222,4027	4695652,764	1,259	1560	1510,4	49,6
386984,8426	4696592,459	1,585	1673	1633,6	39,4
391050,2706	4695087,314	1,995	1560	1528,7	31,3
397154,1922	4694299,542	1,995	1466	1434,7	31,3
398472,5723	4695568,599	1,995	1476	1444,7	31,3
393595,5089	4697457,112	1,995	1684	1652,7	31,3
396314,1502	4695721,362	1,995	1507	1475,7	31,3
396761,2327	4696899,797	2,512	1545	1520,1	24,9
393880,5232	4697638,254	2,512	1687	1662,1	24,9
383761,7138	4700447,349	3,981	1818	1802,3	15,7
396401,3448	4697714,789	3,981	1625	1609,3	15,7
390372,8776	4696510,689	3,981	1636	1620,3	15,7
397481,0872	4693798,285	3,981	1434	1418,3	15,7
389934,0284	4694671,644	5,012	1580	1567,5	12,5
398513,0245	4696483,174	5,012	1479	1466,5	12,5
387845,0266	4697981,398	5,012	1638	1625,5	12,5
394851,6374	4695567,74	5,012	1560	1547,5	12,5
385389,7795	4700052,765	6,31	1709	1699,1	9,9
397969,0544	4695471,535	6,31	1485	1475,1	9,9
397690,2623	4694701,499	6,31	1477	1467,1	9,9
392885,4168	4695208,879	7,943	1550	1542,1	7,9
390416,1695	4697276,378	7,943	1666	1658,1	7,9

Table 5.1. Final values of resonance frequency computed for 36 stations, in decreasing order. d is inversely proportional to v .

These data reveal that Campo Imperatore is a very thin cover, ranging from 7.9 to 62.5 m, indeed a low amount of terrain. This information is certainly different by the stratigraphic throw measured on the border fault (ADAMOLI et al., 1997; VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998). The surrounding thrustbelt, at its post-collisional maxima, provided with sufficient source for sediment production. This is further demonstrated by glacial landforms N and W of Mt. Scindarella and by extensive quarrying on the S slope of the Gran Sasso Range. Therefore, the above values clearly indicate that erosion:

- a) washed away the prominent portion of deposited material;
- b) further landsculpted remarkable fan systems by channeling and terracing.

Within this picture, transport is clearly reflected by present-day glaci-fluvial drainage, in as much as sharp incisions also highlight the substantial sediment load capacity demonstrated by active channeling. Nevertheless, CaCO₃ dissolution caused by predominant karst and piping was likely capable of subtracting a significant fraction of the alluvial stack, whose provenance was essentially an array of Meso-Cenozoic limestone units.

The architecture underlying Campo Imperatore is shown in **Fig. 5.2**. A few limits in this image were clearly introduced by the large spatial resolution of microtremor stations, if compared to DEM spacing, and by data smoothing for imaging purposes. Moreover, the latter factor presumably enhanced the spectral signature of smaller features, hence possibly raising their geomorphic significance. Notwithstanding, the scenario of the pre-Quaternary setup is reasonably reliable. Two main depocenters stand out:

- 1) S margin of the W sub-basin, underneath present-day Piano Racollo;
- 2) towards SE in the E portion of Campo Imperatore.

Underneath the fan systems of Mt. Brancastello – Mt. Prena a gentle slope is consistent from NW to SE, while two small depressions at N tip of Mt. S. Gregorio di Pagànica indicate sinkholes. The geomorphic role of Cortina Valley is certainly underlined by its sharp incision into bedrock, although it was demonstrated that it was excavated after the first stages of the Rionne – La Canala fan at the end of Middle Pleistocene time. Underneath the significant Cocchiarelle fan, a semi-flat surface occurs, while paleodrainage may have reworked the interface NE of Mt. Paradiso and S of Mt. Camicia, thus perching an elongated depocenter.

The overall gentle and smooth image cannot indeed account for the Mesozoic units and their exact tectonic contacts, since this dataset was not targeted for such objective. However, two considerations can be made with respect to Cortina Valley and Colle dei Trozzi. The former occurs in the topographic low between Mt. Mutri and the N foothills of Mt. Bolza, across a S-verging normal fault (VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998). The sharp trace of Cortina Valley abruptly turns towards S into a gorge and into a tight canyon, instead of proceeding for further 500 m across bedrock and then exiting into the E portion of Campo Imperatore. Nonetheless, the canyon carves for several tenths of m into the Calcare Massiccio Fm., perching a short-cut towards S/SE. This suggests that paleodrainage

Figure 5.2. Isopach map of interface between bedrock and Quaternary infill, overlain onto shaded relief of digital topography. Notice paleoflow paths within and out of the basin, in accordance with early erosional pattern on ancient alluvial bodies (microtremors contours in collaboration with Università della Basilicata; DEM source: Servizio Geologico d'Italia).

was either (a) insufficient to land sculpt into the final (and short) portion of bedrock that separates Scoppaturo from the E basin or (b) favored to proceed E-wards up to Scoppaturo and then left to follow a short-cut S-wards. If the second case applies, it is possible that Cortina Valley perched along a former fault trace.

Regarding Colle dei Trozzi (in the E basin), this bedrock remnant outcrops in the S portion of La Fossa; two normal faults bound it longitudinally, parallel to the mountain front of Mt. S. Vito (GHISSETTI and VEZZANI, 1986; VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998). As it was discussed in § 2, the normal border fault system of Campo Imperatore is thought to be complemented by a number of antithetic and synthetic normal structures. One likely possibility is that Colle dei Trozzi represents the tip of a tilted block, either in a half-graben or in a domino accommodation style (JACKSON et al., 1988), thence also faulted on the opposite side by a normal fault triggered by crestal collapse.

Vertical difference between topography and isopachs of the pre-Quaternary bedrock provide an image of actual thicknesses and their spatial distribution (**Fig. 5.3**). Apart from circle-shaped features, likely to be thickening due to karst suffusion upon sinkholes, there is a remarkable difference between W and E sub-basins. In the former, deposits thicken towards S in Piano Racollo, i.e. away from the border fault system. Current knowledge (D'AGOSTINO et al., 1998; VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998) suggests that S-verging normal faults to adjust the Campo Imperatore border fault underlies the basin itself, which is unlikely to create accommodation space in the direction of throw (LEEDER and GAWTHORPE, 1987; JACKSON and LEEDER, 1994). Therefore, either the W basin was triggered by a N-verging normal fault or the cause of thickening has to be searched elsewhere. In the first case, the objective would be the shoulder S of Piano Racollo, where such a structure could either have ruptured or warped the ground surface. However, no deformation effects were found here, either geological or morphological. Also, such effects are not discernible W and E of Piano Racollo (i.e., across the basin, whose genesis would then be only partial), assuming a deforming fault, close to the ground, capable of creating accommodation space proportional to its hypothetical dimensions and geometry. On the other hand, minor surface ruptures described in this work in the Rionne – La Canala fan could be imagined as an antithetic system. Whatever solution, the above considerations rule the Campo Imperatore border fault s.s. out as a basin-forming structure for this depocenter and rather introduce the possibility of a half-graben geometry.

Figure 5.3. Geometry of the Quaternary fill calculated via differential topography and bedrock/alluvium interface. Thickening in the E basin refers to conspicuous fan systems (microtremors data in collaboration with Università della Basilicata; DEM source: Servizio Geologico d'Italia).

Substantial thickness is found in the E sub-basin, specifically underneath the large

Cocchiarelle fan system and its environs. It is important to stress that, as seen in the bedrock interface, a gentle slope developed here before Quaternary deposition. In other words, the main difference between W and E sub-basins lies in the fact that the depocenter underneath Piano Racollo is reflected by the deepening isopachs, whereas in the E portion sedimentation occurred across a gentle slope. A thickening alluvial stack, whose notable geomorphic impact was discussed in § 4, raised present-day ground surface here. Actually, the fact that modern channeling is sculpting through the topographically highest lobe of this fan was already indicative of the critical load this stack delivers. The Easternmost depocenter here underlies another fan system NW of La Fossa, now no longer active, apart from few present-day aprons. However, this system is no longer feeding the main WNW-ESE drainage system of Campo Imperatore. This line of evidence will be exploited in § 7.

Furthermore, Cocchiarelle and adjoining stack were and are the most producing sources for sedimentary load and they embed NW-SE trending channeling, now no longer active. Consequently, back-sculpting erosion may have exerted its activity essentially E-W. Nevertheless, present-day drainage favors S-bound flowpath, overall the entire basin; therefore the entire Gran Sasso Range undergoes active relative uplift. Sinkholes engulf channeling in Piano Racollo, so we can only interpolate its hypothetical preferential direction from across the plain towards Cortina Valley. The absence of such river incision therefore represents a 'geomorphic gap', in as much as we lack a key indicator of current vertical mobility capable of interfering with the ground surface.

In summary, this geophysical investigation helped to (a) constrain basin-scale geomorphological observations and (b) substantiate the hypothesis that the major border fault is not responsible for the genesis of Campo Imperatore. On the other hand, it led the way to another possible view that could prospectively accommodate active geomorphic features. The next chapter of this research aims at model deformation that would be needed to obtain present-day topography or present-day uplift within the Gran Sasso Range.

6. Border fault: modeling elastic deformation

To constrain hypotheses concerning surface displacement as a consequence of potential active faulting, morphological data are here compared with the deformation that would be needed to produce present-day topography of Campo Imperatore and surrounding uplands.

6.1 Theory of coseismic deformation

Dip-slip faulting is a structural process that generates relief. This circumstance is observed in several examples around the world and its basic principles are fairly understood and commonly accepted (SAVAGE and HASTIE, 1966; KING et al., 1988a/b). An upper layer containing an earthquake fault (or a prospective seismogenic source, to fit this work) retains strength indefinitely and acts elastically but the material beneath relaxes stress at a rate determined by its viscosity (KING et al., 1988a). Consequently, deformation sums across geological time and changes between seismic events on the same source. Originally horizontal geological horizons can be considered as fossilized leveling lines that record large cumulative displacement. Upon this ground, it is possible to compute models as close as possible to the studied structures. These develop within the physical constraints posed by long-term effective elastic thickness (T_E) of the crust, while the asymmetry of uplift to subsidence is notably controlled by sediment budget within a newly-formed basin (KING et al., 1988a).

Modeling coseismic displacement in Campo Imperatore was employed to test the possibility that faults within or bounding the basin may be seismogenic sources. As such, surface displacement field that is expected from the 3-D solution of classical dislocation models was compared and contrasted with the main geomorphic features of the area. This was pursued under the assumption that:

- a) the basin inception and development was/is controlled by the activity of such faults;
- b) their total displacement is the results of cumulative events of stick slip over geological time.

The modeling approach was based on formulations developed by Okada (1985, 1992) in which fault patches are assumed planar, with uniform slip, embedded in a uniform

elastic half-space. Displacement field $u_i(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ due to a dislocation $\Delta u_j(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3)$ across a surface Σ in an isotropic medium is given by (OKADA, 1992):

$$u_i = \frac{1}{F} \iint_{\Sigma} \Delta u_j \left[\lambda \delta_{jk} \frac{\partial u_i^n}{\partial \xi_n} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_i^j}{\partial \xi_k} + \frac{\partial u_i^k}{\partial \xi_j} \right) \right] v_k d\Sigma$$

where v_k is the direction cosine of the normal to the surface element $d\Sigma$. Therefore, internal displacement field u° for dip-slip faulting is expressed as follows:

$$u^\circ = \frac{M_0}{F} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u^2}{\partial \xi_3} + \frac{\partial u^3}{\partial \xi_2} \right) \cos 2\delta + \left(\frac{\partial u^3}{\partial \xi_3} - \frac{\partial u^2}{\partial \xi_2} \right) \sin 2\delta \right]$$

Elastic parameters (Lame's constants λ and μ) were both kept equal to 1. The amount of slip was kept constant and equal to 1 m in all models. Strike, dip, rake, length, width, depth, average slip of the suspected causative faults are derived from input of fault tips coordinates into FaultMapper, an in-house code developed by Dr. Roberto Basili at INGV. Aspect ratio (Length/Width) to define the fault plane (**Fig. 6.1**) is derived from empirical relationships of coseismic rupture dimensions from WELLS & COPPERSMITH (1994). Relationships between fault area, earthquake magnitude, and seismic moment are those by KANAMORI & ANDERSON (1975).

Figure 6.1. 3D geometric and kinematic parameters of a fault plane.

Empirical constant factors employed to derive M_w from the inferred seismogenic source whose fault geometry is known (or suspected) is (WELLS and COPPERSMITH, 1994):

$$M_w = a + b \log A$$

<i>where:</i>	Normal	Reverse	Strike-slip	All
<i>a</i>	3.93	4.33	3.98	4.07
<i>b</i>	1.02	0.90	1.02	0.98
<i>A</i>	Fault plane area (km ²) = Length (L) x Width (W) (for normal faults $W = 1.4997 L^{0.7}$)			

A forward modeling procedure was performed by varying the parameters of the several fault branches of the system. A total of 76 sources were computed, downbroken in 21 combined cases (see Appendix for full listing). Of these, four scenarios were chosen as the most representatives and geologically viable, with constraints and limitations for all of them. A summary of model parameters is reported in **Table 6.1**. The first three cases are named after the Campo Imperatore border fault, while the last is related to another potential structure, hypothetically located underneath the S margin of Piano Racollo.

Lat N	Lon N	Lat S	Lon S	Length (km)	Width (km)	Strike (deg)	Dip (deg)	Rake (deg)	D _{Min} (km)	D _{Max} (km)
Campo Imperatore S-verging single fault										
42.454	13.581	42.411	13.788	17.6	11.2	106	65	270	1.0	11.2
Campo Imperatore S-verging two offset segments										
42.432	13.719	42.404	13.795	7.0	5.9	117	65	270	1.0	6.3
42.454	13.581	42.425	13.685	9.1	7.0	111	65	270	1.0	7.4
Campo Imperatore S-verging two offset segments with S-verging boundary faults and NE-verging strike-slip fault										
42.432	13.719	42.404	13.795	7.0	5.9	117	65	270	1.0	6.3
42.454	13.581	42.425	13.685	9.1	7.0	111	65	270	1.0	7.4
42.441	13.620	42.386	13.668	7.3	5.4	327	85	210	1.0	6.4
42.424	13.555	42.415	13.630	6.2	5.4	99	65	270	1.0	5.9
Racollo N-verging single fault										
42.425	13.550	42.375	13.750	17.3	11.0	289	65	270	1.0	11.0

Table 6.1. Fault parameters for chosen experiments of displacement modeling.

D_{Min} and D_{Max} indicate depth of fault top edge and bottom edge respectively. The former was kept at 1 km throughout, thus implying that a prospective seismogenic source here is not rupturing but, rather, warping the ground surface to an extent capable of enacting tangible signals of landscape shift.

6.2 Single-fault vs. multiple fault solutions

Parameterization and computation of hypothetical seismogenic sources allowed to seek a potential explanation for the present-day arrangement of Campo Imperatore, assuming it undergoes current deformation and that such warping is triggered by a seismically active fault (or a fault system). Information stemming from morphotectonic groundwork provided with an adequate database of geological evidences against which models could be realistically tested.

A single, WNW-ESE SW-verging normal strand (**Fig. 6.2**) was envisaged by some Authors (BONCIO et al., 1999; GALADINI et al. 2000a/b) to be an actively-deforming structure. In fact, the presented model does certainly generate an elongated depocenter, and small-scale drainage evolution could be in accordance with this deformation. Towards the NW tip, CCW shift of flowpath could indicate deepening towards the fault. Major channeling along-strike is likely to be forced through the carved valley at the N base of Mt. S. Gregorio di Pagànica, so it might not be an appropriate landscape indicator. On the SE tip, furthermore, CW drainage shift occurs. These comparable evidences, while indicating

Figure 6.2. Single fault model, to geometrically approximate the arched Gran Sasso Range. Contours model displacement of 1m uniform slip (DEM source: Servizio Geologico d'Italia).

a shift in the local maximum dip direction, could perhaps account for warping towards the center of the basin. Nevertheless, this view shows two main limits:

- a) an inner drainage system should take place in the vicinity of the depocenter (LEEDER and GAWTHORPE, 1987; LEEDER, 2000), whereas Campo Imperatore is gently sloping towards SE;
- b) A single fault strand can roughly approximate the Gran Sasso Range but such geometry is neither reflected by known bedrock geology nor by outcrops of the border fault.

Two en-échelon faults (**Fig. 6.3**), separated by a moderate relay ramp (RAMSAY, 1987), provided with an optically-appealing result which certainly well mimics bedrock arrangement. It provides with a basin splitting, exactly located across Mt. Paradiso, one fact that well fits with known data about the presence of two fully-fledged depocenters. The fault offset system aptly follows the arcuate shape of the Gran Sasso Range, at least towards the center. Nevertheless, previous considerations for paleodrainage here no longer apply, since current maximum dip direction would transversally cut the up-warped margins of displaced ground. The E sub-basin, however, shows a gentle slope, which aptly reflects isopachs of bedrock interface.

Figure 6.3. Two-fault model, to better approximate the offset arches of the Gran Sasso Range. Contours model displacement of 1m uniform slip (DEM source: Servizio Geologico d'Italia).

Since the above model cannot accommodate for all bedrock remnants within Campo Imperatore, an attempt was made to model the basin so as to account for the remaining boundary uplands too (**Fig. 6.4**). In this case, displacement field aptly frames the basin within the known arrangement. The subdivision between E and W portion is kept upon Mt. Paradiso, displacement bends across Mt. Prena, the W portion is clearly identified in its two-fold quasi-triangle boundary. This is essentially due to the Pagànica fault, uplifting Mt. Scindarella and to the Pietranzoni-Racollo left-lateral / oblique-slip line, rupturing the E flank of Mt. S. Gregorio di Pagànica. This scenario, however, requires that:

- the Pagànica fault uplifts Mt. Scindarella, which however was likely already a high-relief since it is the uppermost thrust sheet across the Gran Sasso Range;
- additional SSW-verging faults would be required to fully frame the basin margin to the S (downthrowing S of Fosso di Pagànica is not documented);
- the oblique-slip shear zone must have acted at last. Furthermore, its geomorphic impact is such that, if active, the overall faulting sequence would entail a deformation rate incompatible for this area. We are therefore possibly looking at a

Figure 6.4. Four-fault model, to approximate the offset arches of the Gran Sasso Range and architecture of NW basin. Contours model displacement of 1m uniform slip (*DEM source: Servizio Geologico d'Italia*).

long-gone fault array, whose landscape was then underlined by recent morphoselection.

So far we concentrated on bedrock arrangement, assuming an active fault has been capable of downthrowing the S limb of the Gran Sasso Range. While it is certainly possible that such structure, already documented in bedrock geology (VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998), has been deforming up to present-day, the floodplain indicates another accommodation history that can be summarized as follows:

- 1) microtremor measurements highlighted the presence of a depocenter thickening towards the S margin of Piano Racollo, while the rest of the Quaternary/bedrock interface gently slopes SE-ward;
- 2) the E basin shows that recent sedimentation occurred in the Cocchiarelle alluvial fan, and thickened although there is no suitable depocenter;
- 3) the overall floodplain and past/abandoned flowpath plunge towards ESE, thus indicating the former maximum dip direction for the basin. Abandoned drainage implies the latter is being diverted towards another direction (SCHUMM, 1986);
- 4) present-day sedimentation and high-energy drainage is S-bound. This is reflected by the CCW (NW tip) and CW (SE) drainage shift, an evidence that would contradict an active deepening close to the Campo Imperatore border fault.

On these grounds, a further model was run, introducing the possibility of a completely different geometry of deformation (**Fig. 6.5**). Such a fault, from Fosso di Pagànica to the S limb of Mt. Bolza, could be downthrowing Piano Racollo, thus justifying S-bound modern drainage (capable of channeling upslope and of breaching the bedrock, in the case of the Cocchiarelle fan) and the general shift from SE-bound flowpath (hence the overall dip of the floodplain as a result of SE-wards surface transport) to S-bound network of seasonal drainage and fresh fan aprons.

Nevertheless, lack of two lines of evidence constrain the viability of this model:

- 1) towards NW, such fault would possibly interact with the Assergi – Mt. S. Franco fault tip, a large, known SSW-verging normal fault. The two contrasting directions of throw would entail a major accommodation zone which is more common in very large oblique rift environments (MCCLAY, 1995) and less expected to occur in the complex tectonic interplay of Central Italy, resulting from extensional tectonics overlain onto post-collisional structures;

Figure 6.5. Single-fault model, to approximate the genesis of the Racollo depocenter and S-bound active drainage. Contours model displacement of 1m uniform slip (*DEM source: Servizio Geologico d'Italia*).

- 2) such hypothetical fault would not be easy to pinpoint on the S margin of Campo Imperatore. In fact, a large number of WNW-ESE trending structures occur there, some of them N-verging (especially at the S-limb of Mt. Bolza). Therefore, from a kinematic viewpoint, such a fault would be a viable half-graben, deep-rooted onto a splay of the pre-existing Campo Imperatore border fault. However, no direct evidence of warping can be found in the floodplain (the place to look for evidences of recent deformation), apart from minor and contradictory fracturing (see § 4.5). Accordingly, such a structure would deform and uplift bedrock, from which scarce geomorphic information can be obtained in this area.

In summary, if active and seismogenic deformation occurs in Campo Imperatore, a N-verging fault would be the most consistent option with present-day landscape evolution. The latter, indeed, circumscribes a past deformation stage whose geomorphic signature is currently being altered by superposed differential uplift between the Gran Sasso Range and its S environs. After all, seismological record for such hypothetical seismogenic source (or for any source at all) is still unknown in this basin.

7. Morphotectonic model of Campo Imperatore

To determine recent and prospectively active landscape evolution of this intermontane basin, an array of data, either geological/geomorphological, geophysical or arising from modeling of coseismic displacement, was examined and contrasted. Herewith, an overview of arisen issues, reconstructed through interpreted events, allow to devise a new structural interpretation of recent deformation and to infer its potential outcome.

7.1 From collision to extension: accommodation space

A number of Authors stated that Campo Imperatore is basin generated by a S/SW-verging normal fault (**Fig. 7.1**; GALADINI and GIULIANI, 1991; BIGI et al., 1997; D'AGOSTINO et al., 1994a/b; D'AGOSTINO and TOZZI, 1995; D'AGOSTINO et al., 1997; D'AGOSTINO et al., 1998) and that this structure could exert an active deforming role up to recent time (CARRARO and GIARDINO, 1992; BONCIO et al., 1999; GALADINI et al., 2000a/b). These concepts may not necessarily imply one another. In other words, a fault can be causative of a basin but no longer deform it after a given stage; conversely, an active fault, although likely to re-activate pre-existing weakness zones (if of compatible geometry with the new stress field) or inherit topographic control (D'AGOSTINO et al.,

Figure 7.1. 3D diagram of the Gran Sasso Range. The schematic cross section shows a model of structural setting including Campo Imperatore and antithetic fault domain. In this model, the lower Gran Sasso thrust has been extensionally reactivated, causing downthrowing of the Campo Imperatore border fault and ancillary antithetic faulting, adjusting to deformation with CCW block-tilting (*reprinted, from: D'AGOSTINO et al., 1998*).

1997), may deform through a previously undisturbed medium, if favorably oriented. While extensional deformation of the backlimb of the Gran Sasso Range is a documented and well accepted evidence (VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998), viewed through a post-orogenic stage, it is less straightforward to correlate such fault system to the adjoining basin. This statement would imply that a basin-forming fault bounds an elongated depocenter (**Fig. 7.2**; LEEDER and GAWTHORPE, 1987; LEEDER, 2001), with a thickness proportional to fault geometry and kinematics (and fault arrays within and around the invoked shear zone) and accommodated onto a surface-warping displacement field. However, new geophysical data presented in this work demonstrated that there is no genetic relationship between past activity of the Campo Imperatore border fault and the basin. Its architecture does not reflect accommodation space created by lowering of the S limb of the Gran Sasso Chain, which merely embeds a very thin depositional cover, especially if compared with the ~ 700 m stratigraphic throw ascribed to the border fault (VEZZANI and GHISSETTI, 1998).

Figure 7.2. Main sedimentological features of intra-basin facies model. **A:** continental basin with interior drainage. Only the major basin-margin fault is shown; in nature, the presence of antithetic, synthetic and transfer fault systems strongly modify certain depositional reactions to tilting. In addition, the sub-surface geometry is modified by differential compaction, thinning of the hanging wall associated with development of the roll-over and antithetic/synthetic fault systems within the sedimentary cover. **B:** continental basin with axial through-drainage. Note the large alluvial fans sourced in the zone between the two en échelon normal faults and preferential avulsion of the axial river channel(s) towards the faults (*redrawn, from: LEEDER and GAWTHORPE, 1987*).

Moreover, stratigraphic relationships between the W and E portions of Campo Imperatore (Auct.; **Fig. 7.3**), compared with geophysical and geomorphological data, demonstrated that this floodplain is more appropriately defined as a twin basin system, with sensibly different stories and facies, although depositional environments were fairly comparable.

Figure 7.3. Role of Mt. Paradiso as the geomorphic expression of the Campo Imperatore two-basin layout. Notice the stratigraphic record (*Auct.*) lengthening towards NW (upper portion of the basin), in contrast with that of the SE region, where erosional threshold triggered cut terraces.

The sedimentary record is remarkably different between the two sub-areas, mostly for two reasons:

- a) to NW, a thick, intermittent moraine system interfingered with lacustrine deposits, coarse alluvium and a conspicuous fan system entrenched within physiographic boundaries inherited from bedrock assemblage. Depositional systems prevail and are overall best preserved, except for Piano Racollo, which underwent extensive carving; a lacustrine environment subsequently developed, eventually sealed by outer moraine ribbons. These, in turn, underwent extensive karst piping;
- b) to SE, neither glacial deposits nor forms were detected, whereas the topographically lowermost sediments occur, herewith thought to be the oldest ones in Campo Imperatore (via new paleomagnetic data; **Fig. 7.4**). Extensive terracing proves the predominant role of linear erosion, triggered by thresholds bounding the basin (Cretarola and Cortina Valley).

A synoptic summary of geological knowledge gathered in this work is outlined in a cross-section covering Piano Racollo and its bedrock environs (**Fig. 7.5**). Six main stages can be identified:

- 1) pre-Quaternary faulting of Meso-Cenozoic terranes;
- 2) carving of bedrock due to advancement of early glacial fronts;
- 3) early moraines and inception of alluvial fan system;

Figure 7.4. Demagnetization steps (in mT) measured from samples of lacustrine clays, outcropping in the lowermost section of the Campo Imperatore depositional stack. Since the analysis unveils a positive value and since all Quaternary deposition within Campo Imperatore is continental, such deposits are younger than 730 ky (*computed with Fabio Speranza, INGV*).

- 4) landsculpting across Cortina Valley and out in the valley floor;
- 5) deposition of glaci-fluvial terrain and distal moraines;
- 6) recent channeling.

Concerning 1), faulting is ascribed to a post-orogenic SW-verging extensional phase, already well known in literature and well expressed in bedrock outcrops towards SW of Campo Imperatore. The majority of synthetic structures can be connected to S-throwing of the border fault. However, Miocene normal faulting, generally coaxial with the infra-Quaternary one, is documented around Mt. Camicia and other reliefs (ADAMOLI et al., 1997), so these structures may well be emerging today and appear as if they deformed bedrock in a single stage, which contrasts with geological data. This is important in as much co-linear structures that seem to share a common genesis are possibly found in Campo Imperatore (§ 4) and may have well ceased their deformation-prone stage.

Glacial valley landsculpting was highlighted by microtremor investigation, which reported the picture (with known limitations) of a smooth bedrock-Quaternary interface. The absence of a basin developed aside a deforming Campo Imperatore border fault suggests this was no longer down-throwing its S flank since Middle Pleistocene time.

Glacial exaration and abrasion was thence followed by early conspicuous moraine deposits, which covered the overall Piano Racollo and also built up early layers of the Rionne fan system. The latter partly accommodated onto already faulted bedrock by differential compaction across weakness zones, whose geometry was inherited from the lower interface. This prospectively explains minor fractures on the lowermost Rionne fan

Figure 7.5 Schematic geological cross-section of the W portion of the Campo Imperatore basin, with profile including projection of the Mt. Paradiso - Mt. Mutri from adjacent E. Also, Valle Cortina erosional threshold, with its buried gorge (thence depocenter) is projected from farther E.

lobe, then sealed by later aprons, since we already determined that S-verging faulting was no longer active at this stage.

Distinct landsculpting across Cortina Valley was in part triggered by the Tavo River upper reach and, realistically, by an overall sharp lowering of the base level. A wide-reaching erosional process excavated almost all Piano Racollo, leaving only few remnants of earlier moraines that acted as consolidated river bars. However, carving markedly acted towards the S margin of the eroded moraines, thus generating the depocenters revealed by newly-acquired geophysical data.

By the stage glaci-fluvial and outer moraines were emplaced, the depocenter was deepening on its S margin, where lacustrine deposits, currently outcropping in Piano Racollo with remnants of the terminal glaciation (JAURAND, 1998; KOTARBA et al, 2001), sealed external moraine systems. Further channeling, highlighted by soil water content via Landsat TM data (§ 4.5), eventually sculpted the glacial and lacustrine landscape.

7.2 Active faulting: geomorphic and seismotectonic inconsistencies

Comparing and contrasting geological evidences of landscape signals with prospective deformation models indeed underlines the fact that some evidences could either fit more than one possible scenarios or mismatch viable interpretations.

From a morphotectonic viewpoint, some issues outstand:

- 1) elements ascribable to recent/active deformation (i.e., the fractures on the lowermost lobe of the Rionne – La Canala fan) show modest geomorphic expression. These are remarkably parallel and aligned with major structures across a wide bedrock portion (likely with a dip-slip mechanism, of uncertain vergence, possibly inherited by previous tectonic phases). Since ruptures do not interfere with *both* bedrock *and* alluvium, such structures are thought to be of non-tectonic origin;
- 2) active or incipient deformation is underlined by recent channeling and fan apron evolution, all indicating that either the Gran Sasso Range is being uplifted or that lowering occurs towards the S margin of Campo Imperatore – or, in fact, both, for a single cause;

- 3) such deformation is difficult to be associated with activity (or reactivation) of the Campo Imperatore border fault, given its geometry, localization of prospective displacement and information about the actual position of sedimentary depocenters, geometrically and genetically not connected with the border fault, as it was previously thought (Auct.);
- 4) this is further underlined by topography data (**Fig. 7.6**), showing that the basin consistently dips towards SE. This feature was clearly enhanced by extensive and wide-reaching erosion, triggered by breached thresholds. These latter, however, cut through the already lowermost section of the early-stage floodplain, i.e. terracing and incision was already following its direction of preferential transport.

Figure 7.6. Drainage-wise sharpened DEM, as a basis to show relationship among border faults, floodplain topography and pattern of major linear erosional processes controlling sediment dispersal out of Campo Imperatore. Pietrattina threshold is deemed to be the main breach, back-sculpting into Cortina Valley and thence forced to leave ancient path as feeding from NE alluvial systems decreased (10m digitized contours © Regione Abruzzo, courtesy of IRTR – CNR; 230m grid, provided by Servizio Geologico d'Italia).

On a seismotectonic ground, different points arise:

- 1) coseismic deformation needed to model the overall topography of the Gran Sasso Range, Campo Imperatore and its surrounding bedrock uplands requires a number of faults, all of them assumed to be actively deforming and capable of events with an adequately ground-warping behavior (i.e., $M > 5/5.5$; VALENSISE and PANTOSTI, 2001);

- 2) the four-fault model best approximates the geometric relationship between basin and adjoining reliefs. Nevertheless, the geomorphic maturity of such faults and their poorly-spaced geometric interplay suggests such structures would not be actively deforming, especially since the last active source would possibly be the oblique-slip one. While such kinematics is fairly likely for a fault displacing the E flank of Mt. S. Gregorio di Pagànica, there are neither geomorphic nor geophysical evidences that this fault is either creating or rejuvenating accommodation space in the basin;
- 3) the two-fault model is an acceptable approximation of the Gran Sasso Range and of the two-fold nature of Campo Imperatore. On the ground of their geometric parameters (BONILLA, 1984; BULL, 1987) such faults would invoke recurrence times likely to be within the Historical Catalogue (i.e., within the last 2 ka). However, such official compilation does not acknowledge suitable events in the area and not with the M value needed for surface deformation;
- 4) the S-verging one-fault model, computed according to published seismotectonic maps for Central Italy, suggests such deformation is unlikely, since (a) the Gran Sasso Range does not morphologically fit the prospective footwall and (b) geophysical and topographic indicate lowering and accommodation space towards S, i.e. away from fault trace occurrence;
- 5) the N-verging one-fault model is thought to be the most appropriate to fit present-day S-bound flowpath migration and accommodation space markedly thickening on the S margin of Piano Racollo. However, this fault is not easy to locate on the incoherent bedrock geomorphology, where karst dissection sensibly obliterates geomorphic signature of deformation. Nevertheless, for both single-fault models, recurrence time would prospectively be longer than the time-span covered by the official catalogue. In both cases, this would be an explanation for the lack of seismic record. Furthermore, while the Campo Imperatore border fault is a very prominent feature, herewith thought to be no longer active, N-verging structures are known in the S margin of Campo Imperatore. From a kinematic viewpoint, this suggests that an actively deforming structure there could be re-activating a minor fault or, pushing interpretation one step further, deformation could be at its inception stage.

7.3 Genesis and development of the Campo Imperatore basin

This research demonstrated that the area of investigation, commonly thought to be a syn-tectonic basin of its border fault, itself in turn actively deforming, is in fact a depocenter excavated on the hanging-wall of a large structure, no longer active since Middle Pleistocene time. Rather, the actual depocenter developed only towards the end of the Pleistocene and fully deepened during Holocene time. A causative fault for a graben system is envisaged in a N-verging structure, whose deformation is exerting control on present-day drainage system, sensibly different from the ancient one inherited from the floodplain ground surface. **Fig. 7.7** summarizes this view:

- 1) The end of Pliocene represents the termination of the Apennine contractional regime (Auct.). Its landscape is composed by stacked thrust sheets of intensely deformed (both by reverse and normal faulting) Meso-Cenozoic terranes. Its remnants are today visible in the Gran Sasso Range, Mt. Bolza and Mt. Scindarella.
- 2) In the lower portion of the Pleistocene, major normal faulting, S/SW verging, intensely displaces the thrustsedimentary succession by 700+ m (Auct.), partitioning slip across a number of splays.
- 3) In the upper portion of the Pleistocene, antithetic NE-verging faults downthrow the pre-existent hanging-wall. Breccias infill the top of the S domino system (D'AGOSTINO ET AL., 1994A/B; D'AGOSTINO AND TOZZI, 1995), while glacial exaration, followed by moraine sedimentation, builds up the first sedimentary stages of N Campo Imperatore.
- 4) At the Pleistocene – Holocene boundary, a tectonically quiet stage leaves room to a general uplift of the entire tectonic edifice causes abrupt fall in the base level. This leads to the breaching of the Tavo River upper reach and its back-sculpting incision. This cuts through bedrock and Pleistocene glacial deposits, altering the landscape and eventually connecting the W and E sectors of Campo Imperatore via the Valley Cortina threshold.
- 5) Since the Holocene / Recent time, a N-verging fault is being reactivated and downthrows the Southernmost portion of the floodplain. Such faulting, possibly cutting through minor splays of the Campo Imperatore border fault, enhances the overall S-

Morphotectonic signature of the Campo Imperatore Quaternary basin (Central Apennines): implications for the seismotectonics of Central Italy

Umberto Fracassi
Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra
Università degli Studi di Firenze
Italy

Figure 7.7. Evolution of the Gran Sasso Range - Campo Imperatore fault system and depocenter. All profiles are from SW to NE (direction of maximum tectonic transport, Auct.). Not in scale.

bound slope of the basin, causing current drainage to react to block tilting, reflected by deepening of the depocenter towards S.

7.4 The role of Campo Imperatore in Central Italy

How can insight of the seismotectonic scenario in Central Italy benefit from this newly-formed interpretation? Most active or prospectively active normal structures in this complex sector of the Apennines are essentially SW-verging. A limited number of these faults have been recognized as likely seismogenic sources (VALENSISE and PANTOSTI, 2001). This implies that determining the seismic potential of a structure requires a vast amount of data and over a relatively long time-span. Such data include but are certainly not limited to geological evidence of coseismic surface rupture or seismological record. As field geology is progressively providing with a picture of prospective structures within an acceptable error limit, records (either historical or, for recent events, instrumental) are intrinsically limited, although of critical importance. Likewise, information stemming from adjoining fields of research, like fine-scale geomorphology and geomorphometry (exploited in this work), thermal remote sensing, numerical modeling of surface erosion and sediment dispersal, paleoseismology, among other procedures, all provide with subtle yet key evidences of deformation – or of its absence. Even better, these approaches and their combination is likely to highlight contradictions in knowledge gaps that only fine-scale detail can show.

This research proposes a rather different interpretation of a potentially active fault, N-verging, for which no seismological record exist but geomorphological evidences do, further substantiated by new geophysical data. The structure herewith underlined discusses and opposes models so far published for this area, which has always been of difficult interpretation due to its subtle and somewhat contradicting evidences. Affirming that the Campo Imperatore border fault is neither causative of nor deforming the basin implies that topographic control is not sufficient to initiate re-activation of the fault itself. Consequently, this introduces doubts as to determining prospectively active structures on the sole ground of their topographic signature, since this research demonstrated that this approach can be misleading. Deformation in the Central Apennines does not resemble that of other regions of the world, like the Basin and Range, Tibet or Tien Shan (ZHANG et al., 1991; JACKSON and

LEEDER, 1994; FOTHERGILL and MA, 1999; KORJENKOV et al., 1999; VAN DER WOERD et al., 2000); rather, it tends to be less evident yet destructive, since these areas are densely populated. This implies that proactive views of unclear regions may help to ascertain what structures need to be further investigated to fill the voids of geological knowledge. Is Campo Imperatore still one of these?

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My sister, Loredana Fracassi, endured a tragic battle with something too much bigger than her – and lost. Her loss unsurprisingly determined an absolute and immense shift into my very gestures and into my philosophical thought and inquiry. Apart from a personal development, which was needed and part of the long-term reaction, the tragedy entailed a daily struggle and psychological turmoil which, surprisingly (but perhaps not) unveiled how strong was my passion for research and geology. It highlighted my quest for brainpower in times when only rational, scientific thought could pose a levee to the insatiable pain. This thesis is dedicated to her memory, forever vivid.

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Appendixes

A.1 Environmental microtremors

Microtremor stations

Date	Location	Eastings	Northings	GPS elev.	DEM-IGM aver. El.	N. of recs.
10/10/01	Lago Pietranzoni	386854,5884	4698306,156	1640	1645,0	5
10/10/01	Caselle	384451,7704	4699645,054	1770	1739,0	5
10/10/01	M. Scindareella NW	383526,4504	4700053,634	1855	1838,0	4
10/10/01	Osservatorio E	383065,5206	4700137,985	1875	1869,0	5
10/10/01	Vado di Como alto	384090,0089	4700748,446	1855	1845,0	5
10/10/01	Vado di Como basso	383761,7138	4700447,349	1830	1810,0	5
10/10/01	Mandruce N	385389,7795	4700052,765	1710	1709,5	5
10/10/01	Mandruce E	385723,4943	4699985,091	1700	1709,0	5
10/10/01	Mandruce S	385572,7401	4699521,063	1670	1684,5	5
10/10/01	M. San Gregorio di Paganica N	385444,3815	4699369,891	1685	1699,5	5
05/07/01	Lago Racollo	389934,0284	4694671,644	1535	1576,5	5
05/08/01	Colle Racollo	391050,2706	4695087,314	1530	1560,0	5
05/08/01	La Fossa S	397969,0544	4695471,535	1435	1481,5	5
05/08/01	Fonte Vetica	396401,3448	4697714,789	1585	1627,5	5
05/08/01	La Fossa N	398513,0245	4696483,174	1445	1483,5	5
11/10/01	M. San Gregorio di Paganica N2	386129,3706	4699146,535	1620	1664,5	5
11/10/01	S. Egidio	387229,7245	4697383,759	1615	1647,5	5
11/10/01	Costa Ceraso	386984,8426	4696592,459	1630	1673,5	5
11/10/01	Val Coppone	387749,5966	4695883,722	1640	1661,0	5
11/10/01	Le Capannelle	388669,4705	4695239,243	1570	1610,0	5
11/10/01	Le Capannelle E	389595,0294	4695204,564	1550	1585,5	5
11/10/01	Lago Racollo N	390343,6378	4695067,269	1530	1573,0	5
11/10/01	Sella S. Cristoforo N	390573,6649	4694721,575	1535	1569,0	5
11/10/01	La Canala S	390598,0837	4695755,23	1550	1582,5	5
11/10/01	Valle Cortina 1	391439,0328	4694994,63	1525	1558,0	5
11/10/01	Valle Cortina 2	391819,7721	4695127,559	1515	1551,5	5
11/10/01	Valle Cortina 3	392462,9446	4695250,91	1510	1544,0	5
11/10/01	Valle Cortina 4	392885,4168	4695208,879	1505	1545,0	5
11/10/01	Valle Cortina 5	393358,0338	4695323,822	1505	1548,5	5
11/10/01	Valle Cortina 6	393700,7916	4695452,988	1500	1539,5	5
12/10/01	Stazzo del Lepre SW	386707,5593	4699082,7	1625	1652,5	5
12/10/01	Stazzo del Lepre SE	387831,7897	4698540,291	1635	1660,5	5
12/10/01	M. Faeto W	388361,5511	4698223,025	1640	1672,5	5
12/10/01	M. Faeto SW	387845,0266	4697981,398	1605	1638,5	5
12/10/01	Piano di Pietranzoni	387498,4998	4697975,867	1610	1637,5	5
12/10/01	Le Coppe di S. Stefano	388697,714	4695771,922	1580	1618,5	5
12/10/01	Fonte Rionne S1	390416,1695	4697276,378	1640	1663,5	5
12/10/01	Fonte Rionne S2	390372,8776	4696510,689	1610	1633,0	5
12/10/01	Fonte Rionne S3	390429,6738	4695828,953	1560	1591,0	5
13/10/01	Fonte di Cretarola	397481,0872	4693798,285	1405	1436,0	5
13/10/01	Piano dell'ospedale 1	397154,1922	4694299,542	1445	1468,0	5
13/10/01	Piano dell'Ospedale 2	396860,0113	4694671,5	1460	1486,5	5
13/10/01	Colle S.Francesco E	397690,2623	4694701,499	1455	1473,5	5
13/10/01	N/NW di Colle S.Francesco	396810,3592	4695378,6	1470	1496,0	5
13/10/01	Pietrattina	398472,5723	4695568,599	1450	1476,0	5
13/10/01	La Fossa W	396761,2327	4696899,797	1540	1547,0	5
13/10/01	Valle della Macina 1	396319,1494	4696279,942	1505	1511,5	5
13/10/01	Valle della Macina 2	395564,2	4697090,859	1550	1567,0	5
13/10/01	Incrocio NW Fonte della Macina	395767,07	4696071,583	1535	1541,5	5
13/10/01	Cocchiarelle N	394805,4031	4696596,901	1610	1602,5	5
13/10/01	I Caldai W	393880,5232	4697638,254	1704	1689,0	5

13/10/01	I Caldai SW	393595,5089	4697457,112	1695	1683,5	5
13/10/01	Cocchiarelle S	394851,6374	4695567,74	1570	1559,0	5
14/10/01	Le Fosse E	393596,4747	4696062,107	1620	1599,5	5
14/10/01	Canali di Marcegli N	394222,4027	4695652,764	1580	1565,0	5
14/10/01	Fonte della Macina	396314,1502	4695721,362	1525	1506,0	5
14/10/01	Colle dei Trozzi SW	397468,2364	4696064,174	1515	1499,0	5
14/10/01	Colle dei Trozzi NE	397854,8073	4696327,285	1515	1499,0	5

Border points

Location	Eastings	Northings	DEM-IGM aver. Elev.
	382478,6545	4701037,888	2167,0
	383660,6047	4700869,784	1977,0
	384470,8132	4701218,272	1947,5
	383056,0246	4700044,105	1873,0
	385739,7291	4698614,016	1741,0
	385815,5543	4700588,262	1797,0
	386853,198	4699835,941	1754,0
	388479,3117	4698486,832	1686,0
	389399,498	4697834,484	1655,0
	391102,6104	4698031,842	1793,5
	392514,6952	4697722,02	1801,5
M. Paradiso	391437,2812	4696942,239	1708,0
M. Paradiso	392732,1209	4696627,44	1649,0
M. Paradiso	391358,6415	4696214,216	1623,5
M. Paradiso	391535,4122	4695400,483	1577,5
M. Paradiso	392449,3418	4695386,092	1571,0
M. Paradiso	393233,1024	4696203,686	1609,5
	393727,2906	4697908,881	1713,5
	395416,3015	4697743,114	1673,5
	397049,6509	4698025,96	1617,5
	398133,5356	4697133,191	1523,5
	398882,8311	4696042,29	1476,0
Colle dei Trozzi	397700,5081	4696159,455	1498,5
Colle dei Trozzi	397584,499	4696085,271	1495,5
Colle dei Trozzi	397569,4975	4696253,063	1502,5
Colle dei Trozzi	397803,6133	4695955,315	1491,0
	399075,9334	4695136,766	1466,5
	399202,7807	4694791,096	1478,5
	398070,5614	4695443,625	1493,0
	397846,359	4694708,593	1485,0
	397838,1414	4693697,572	1445,0
	397099,495	4693871,912	1464,0
	396029,0303	4695025,808	1499,0
	394616,3426	4695135,958	1525,5
	392457,7104	4695189,167	1551,0
	391505,5125	4694817,201	1559,0
	389964,181	4694514,551	1571,5
	388287,7019	4695504,237	1638,5
	385940,6312	4696898,794	1674,5
	387035,9308	4697326,158	1686,5
	386935,3421	4698102,162	1647,0
	384305,7268	4699268,189	1806,0
	382201,365	4700162,594	1974,5
	383542,2309	4699738,325	1815,0
	390526,3444	4694552,933	1570,0
	398706,1402	4695380,702	1473,5
	396877,6191	4694454,878	1477,5
	395277,1175	4695067,153	1525,5
	393893,1915	4695446,046	1573,0
M. Paradiso	393256,3254	4695379,894	1566,5
M. Paradiso	393654,8803	4695537,005	1567,5
	393597,3569	4695392,297	1548,5
	393264,5431	4695268,262	1548,5

External points

Location	Eastings	Northings	DEM-IGM aver. Elev.
	382478,6545	4701342,877	2378,0
	383641,6001	4701165,243	2168,5
	385185,1987	4701352,883	1981,5
	382875,4811	4699700,991	1935,5
	385777,7383	4698366,212	1889,0
	385958,0886	4700874,19	1951,5
	387109,7598	4700169,523	1950,0
	388669,3575	4698810,883	1741,5
	389608,5483	4698234,783	1821,0
	391188,131	4698374,955	1853,0
	392581,2112	4698017,478	1900,5
M. Paradiso	391760,3591	4696675,373	1807,5
M. Paradiso	392513,5682	4696265,265	1690,0
M. Paradiso	392403,8933	4695718,608	1699,5
	393466,0867	4695004,855	1625,0
	393860,3226	4698280,587	1791,5
	395264,2648	4698019,51	1827,5
	397182,6829	4698483,444	1825,0
	398299,8256	4697285,686	1652,0
	399006,3608	4696123,303	1511,5
Colle dei Trozzi	397683,525	4696081,506	1498,0
	399213,7166	4695193,952	1509,0
	399416,5822	4694648,133	1492,5
	398251,1049	4694995,672	1518,0
	398273,962	4694489,382	1480,5
	398265,7444	4693354,459	1534,5
	397280,0385	4693271,464	1575,0
	395991,0212	4694663,633	1526,5
	394815,8907	4694802,375	1540,5
	392495,7196	4695017,611	1610,0
	391648,0469	4694512,211	1726,0
	389764,6329	4694238,154	1589,5
	388021,6378	4695265,964	1684,5
	386634,2982	4696422,248	1810,5
	386598,8255	4697392,875	1773,5
	386811,8123	4697844,827	1770,0
	384305,7268	4698896,483	1926,5
	381944,8032	4700038,692	2056,0
	383399,6966	4699366,619	1886,0
	390716,3902	4694238,412	1656,0
	398786,9096	4694904,156	1503,0
	396763,5916	4694207,075	1477,5
	394026,2235	4695093,402	1571,0
	393493,3414	4695670,438	1597,5

A.2 Full results of coseismic displacement model

ID	LatN	lonN	latS	lonS	Length km	Width km	Strike deg	Dip deg	Rake deg	Min_dep th km	Max_dep th km
1	42.454	13.581	42.411	13.788	17.6	11.2	106	65	270	1.0	11.1
2	42.432	13.719	42.404	13.795	7.0	5.9	117	65	270	1.0	6.3
2	42.454	13.581	42.425	13.685	9.1	7.0	111	65	270	1.0	7.4
3	42.440	13.696	42.404	13.796	9.1	7.0	116	65	270	1.0	7.4
3	42.454	13.581	42.418	13.706	11.0	8.0	111	65	270	1.0	8.3
4	42.437	13.724	42.404	13.795	6.9	5.8	122	65	270	1.0	6.3

4	42.437	13.716	42.429	13.668	4.0	4.0	77	65	270	1.0	4.6
4	42.454	13.581	42.432	13.660	6.9	5.8	111	65	270	1.0	6.3
5	42.426	13.760	42.399	13.795	4.2	6.6	136	65	270	1.0	7.0
5	42.434	13.721	42.428	13.755	2.9	6.6	103	65	270	1.0	7.0
5	42.435	13.714	42.429	13.668	3.8	3.8	80	65	270	1.0	4.5
5	42.449	13.609	42.432	13.660	4.6	7.7	114	65	270	1.0	8.0
5	42.451	13.602	42.447	13.573	2.4	7.7	79	65	270	1.0	8.0
12	42.454	13.581	42.411	13.788	17.6	11.2	106	65	270	1.0	11.1
12	42.441	13.620	42.386	13.668	7.3	5.4	327	85	210	1.0	6.4
12	42.424	13.555	42.415	13.630	6.2	5.4	99	65	270	1.0	5.9
22	42.432	13.719	42.404	13.795	7.0	5.9	117	65	270	1.0	6.3
22	42.454	13.581	42.425	13.685	9.1	7.0	111	65	270	1.0	7.4
22	42.441	13.620	42.386	13.668	7.3	5.4	327	85	210	1.0	6.4
22	42.424	13.555	42.415	13.630	6.2	5.4	99	65	270	1.0	5.9
32	42.440	13.696	42.404	13.796	9.1	7.0	116	65	270	1.0	7.4
32	42.454	13.581	42.418	13.706	11.0	8.0	111	65	270	1.0	8.3
32	42.441	13.620	42.386	13.668	7.3	5.4	327	85	210	1.0	6.4
32	42.424	13.555	42.415	13.630	6.2	5.4	99	65	270	1.0	5.9
42	42.437	13.724	42.404	13.795	6.9	5.8	122	65	270	1.0	6.3
42	42.437	13.716	42.429	13.668	4.0	4.0	77	65	270	1.0	4.6
42	42.454	13.581	42.432	13.660	6.9	5.8	111	65	270	1.0	6.3
42	42.441	13.620	42.386	13.668	7.3	5.4	327	85	210	1.0	6.4
42	42.424	13.555	42.415	13.630	6.2	5.4	99	65	270	1.0	5.9
52	42.426	13.760	42.399	13.795	4.2	6.6	136	65	270	1.0	7.0
52	42.434	13.721	42.428	13.755	2.9	6.6	103	65	270	1.0	7.0
52	42.435	13.714	42.429	13.668	3.8	3.8	80	65	270	1.0	4.5
52	42.449	13.609	42.432	13.660	4.6	7.7	114	65	270	1.0	8.0
52	42.451	13.602	42.447	13.573	2.4	7.7	79	65	270	1.0	8.0
52	42.441	13.620	42.386	13.668	7.3	5.4	327	85	210	1.0	6.4
52	42.424	13.555	42.415	13.630	6.2	5.4	99	65	270	1.0	5.9
111	42.454	13.581	42.411	13.788	17.6	11.2	106	65	270	1.0	11.1
111	42.424	13.555	42.415	13.630	6.2	5.4	99	65	270	1.0	5.9
211	42.432	13.719	42.404	13.795	7.0	5.9	117	65	270	1.0	6.3
211	42.454	13.581	42.425	13.685	9.1	7.0	111	65	270	1.0	7.4
211	42.424	13.555	42.415	13.630	6.2	5.4	99	65	270	1.0	5.9
311	42.440	13.696	42.404	13.796	9.1	7.0	116	65	270	1.0	7.4
311	42.454	13.581	42.418	13.706	11.0	8.0	111	65	270	1.0	8.3
311	42.424	13.555	42.415	13.630	6.2	5.4	99	65	270	1.0	5.9
411	42.437	13.724	42.404	13.795	6.9	5.8	122	65	270	1.0	6.3
411	42.437	13.716	42.429	13.668	4.0	4.0	77	65	270	1.0	4.6
411	42.454	13.581	42.432	13.660	6.9	5.8	111	65	270	1.0	6.3
411	42.424	13.555	42.415	13.630	6.2	5.4	99	65	270	1.0	5.9
511	42.426	13.760	42.399	13.795	4.2	6.6	136	65	270	1.0	7.0
511	42.434	13.721	42.428	13.755	2.9	6.6	103	65	270	1.0	7.0
511	42.435	13.714	42.429	13.668	3.8	3.8	80	65	270	1.0	4.5
511	42.449	13.609	42.432	13.660	4.6	7.7	114	65	270	1.0	8.0
511	42.451	13.602	42.447	13.573	2.4	7.7	79	65	270	1.0	8.0
511	42.424	13.555	42.415	13.630	6.2	5.4	99	65	270	1.0	5.9
112	42.454	13.581	42.411	13.788	17.6	11.2	106	65	270	1.0	11.1
112	42.441	13.620	42.386	13.668	7.3	5.4	327	85	210	1.0	6.4
212	42.432	13.719	42.404	13.795	7.0	5.9	117	65	270	1.0	6.3

212	42.454	13.581	42.425	13.685	9.1	7.0	111	65	270	1.0	7.4
212	42.441	13.620	42.386	13.668	7.3	5.4	327	85	210	1.0	6.4
312	42.440	13.696	42.404	13.796	9.1	7.0	116	65	270	1.0	7.4
312	42.454	13.581	42.418	13.706	11.0	8.0	111	65	270	1.0	8.3
312	42.441	13.620	42.386	13.668	7.3	5.4	327	85	210	1.0	6.4
412	42.437	13.724	42.404	13.795	6.9	5.8	122	65	270	1.0	6.3
412	42.437	13.716	42.429	13.668	4.0	4.0	77	65	270	1.0	4.6
412	42.454	13.581	42.432	13.660	6.9	5.8	111	65	270	1.0	6.3
412	42.441	13.620	42.386	13.668	7.3	5.4	327	85	210	1.0	6.4
512	42.426	13.760	42.399	13.795	4.2	6.6	136	65	270	1.0	7.0
512	42.434	13.721	42.428	13.755	2.9	6.6	103	65	270	1.0	7.0
512	42.435	13.714	42.429	13.668	3.8	3.8	80	65	270	1.0	4.5
512	42.449	13.609	42.432	13.660	4.6	7.7	114	65	270	1.0	8.0
512	42.451	13.602	42.447	13.573	2.4	7.7	79	65	270	1.0	8.0
512	42.441	13.620	42.386	13.668	7.3	5.4	327	85	210	1.0	6.4
610	42.425	13.550	42.375	13.750	17.3	11.0	289	65	270	1.0	11.0